

IMPLEMENTATION OF ADOPT-A-SCHOOL PROGRAM: SUCCESS STORY OF BUENAVISTA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12634742>

ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the successful implementation of Buenavista National High School's (BNHS) Adopt-a-School Programs (ASPs), established through Republic Act No. 8525, and to explore how the school earned two awards for two consecutive years: first runner-up in the division under the mega category and champion in the cluster of Buenavista. Furthermore, this study seeks to identify BNHS' practices that could be benchmarked by other schools and to pinpoint factors needing enhancement to achieve the highest possible recognition. This was through a face-to face interview using a self-constructed guide questionnaire, emphasizing the ASPs' processes: pre-implementation, implementation, post-implementation, and the effects of the projects based on participants' or beneficiaries' perceptions and as reflected in the school report card. Its validity was confirmed by professionals: an Education Program Supervisor, a Research Expert, a Language Expert, and a Statistician. The data were collected through triangulation methods, including in-depth interviews, observation, and documentary analysis, and analyzed using thematic analysis. The responses of program participants, implementing bodies, and school organization members during face-to-face interviews indicated that the ASPs were successful, as evidenced by positive feedback and school report card data. Most ASPs had long-term effects on beneficiaries, as perceived and noted by interviewees. Among the five ASPs at BNHS, two became annual programs, and one was adopted by the Rural Health Unit of the Local Government. The BNHS practices that could be emulated by other schools include formulating short-term ASPs with long-term effects to meet learners' essential needs, leading to annual ASPs that strengthen community linkages; recognizing volunteer groups and stakeholders; providing incentives to outstanding volunteers; and holding "Gabi ng Pagkilala," to recognize various stakeholders' support. Despite BNHS's consistent ranking as first runner-up for two consecutive years in the division and achieving Level 1 in the school

report card, there are areas for improvement. These include consistent adherence to the roles and functions of implementing officers, proper documentation, and accountability in implementing the ASP.

Keywords: *Adopt-a-School Program, Brigada Eskwela, beneficiaries, benchmarking, implementation, donors, sponsors, volunteers, volunteerism, organizations, Memorandum of Agreement, Deed of Donation, Deed of Acceptance*

INTRODUCTION

Presented in this section are the basis of what the researcher will investigate: research questions, hypotheses, and the significance of the study. In this, it was described how the study differs from the other studies and addresses something that is neither yet known nor has been studied before. It also includes the scope, delimitation, and fundamental nature of the study.

Public schools face significant challenges in attaining quality education. One is the lack of resources to further both students and school improvement. Schools could not achieve all the goals and objectives without the support of the community and by merely relying on the government's funds.

To remedy the budget discrepancy, the Department of Education (DepEd) sought the involvement and assistance of private entities to aid public schools in realizing an educational program within an agreed period through Republic Act No. 8525. The Act Establishing an Adopt-a-School Program (ASP), approved on February 14, 1998, is encapsulated in the ASP Toolkit for using generic forms and implementation.

As a counterpart, DepEd has been providing support funds since 2009 to sustain partnership initiatives under the ASP at the regional and division levels, as stated in DepEd Order No. 6 series of 2016, or the so-called Utilization of Support Funds for Adopt-a-School Program. It is intended to support and fund the implementation of Brigada Eskwela (BE), as stated in the 2009 Brigada Eskwela Manual. BE is a unique program of the Department of Education that acts as a frontline activity in dealing with the numerous issues facing Philippine education. From 2020, the allocation was diverted from the former materials for rehabilitating school classrooms to the provision of printing materials for Self-Learning Materials (SLM) for the students because of the changes brought up by COVID-19. Due to this pandemic, the former main objective of DepEd concentrated on providing the students with sufficient learning materials, following the Policy Guidelines for the Provision of Learning Resources in the Implementation of the Basic Education Continuity Plan.

At present, budget allocation has changed because of the improvements in global health. The amount received by the Department of Education from the National Budget for Fiscal Year 2022 supports all the Department's current programs, activities, and projects while paying particular attention to initiatives that support the adoption of blended learning

modalities and the safe and gradual return to face-to-face instruction, such as Flexible Learning Options (FLOs), School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE), Government Assistance and Subsidies.

Regardless of the situation of the country's economic status, schools need the involvement of the community. Daniel (2019) stated that needs of a school, specifically learners, must be satisfied to realize vision and mission of the education that will benefit them. Together, school and community partners can create learning opportunities and access to resources that promote students' growth and learning.

Throughout the fiscal year, more than two-thirds of the governments struggle to keep the anticipated composition of their expenditures. Most industries are impacted by this, particularly those that are service-oriented like education (Kadirov et al., 2023). Thus, consistent support and cooperation of every aspect of the community is indispensable in the realization of every launched project by the school.

To answer the call of the Department of Education, the Division of Marinduque continuously creates various programs under the ASP that could respond to the needs of the learners, eliminating barriers to an effective learning process. Offices designated for this endeavor include the Private Sector Partnerships Unit (PSPU), inclusive of one of the three units handled by the Educational Program Supervisor (EPS) under the different partnership needs of the DepEd, aside from the Government and Community Partnerships Unit (GCPU) and Special Events Unit (SEU).

In support of the ASP of DepEd, Buenavista National High School (BNHS) consistently supports the advocacy of the Office of the Schools Division of Marinduque concerning implementing the national projects. BNHS has persistently sought the cooperation of all stakeholders to implement each ASP launched by the school and the department to suit the needs of the students for the last five years. Among these projects were: Send-off Programs for Players; a Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage; Healing and Firming of Families for a More Holistic Education (HAFFMHE); and the Concreting of BNHS Ground. Aligned with these projects is the National Flag Project of ASP, Brigada Eskwela (BE), which has been conducted every school year and, with the new guidelines, is now a whole-year-round program of the department.

Being a Guidance Designate who untiringly finds ways to improve the learning condition of the students in and out of the school by creating various programs that have been extended to the community for support, the researcher was encouraged to probe the success of the implementation of ASPs in BNHS through the shared experiences of the beneficiaries of the programs under ASP guided by the philosophy, vision, and mission of Homeroom Guidance as mandated by the DepEd Revised Implementation of Homeroom Guidance for School Year 2021-2022. Further, the researcher wishes to identify the various forms of assistance extended to the school and justify the ASP outcomes reflected in the school report card and statements of the beneficiaries of the programs. Likewise, to establish the strong collaborative efforts of family, school, community, government, and other institutions and organizations in realizing projects under the ASP of BNHS.

With the above scenario, the researcher would like to conduct this study to justify the successful implementation of ASP in BNHS through in-depth interviews, with the hope that the results of this study could help improve the implementation of the school's ASPs. Furthermore, the researcher wishes other schools could eventually benchmark those ASPs to provide better services for the clientele and further strengthen connections with other stakeholders. Barret (2023) stated in his paper that escalating commitment in an educational setting demonstrates the ability to create a useful theoretical framework for comprehending the factors that can impede the adoption of school projects. He further discussed that these evidence-based are alternatives in place of low-value practices to justify the success of any school-initiated project.

With great consideration and appreciation for the varied assistance from the sponsors, consistent support from stakeholders, and the efforts of the project coordinators of the ASPs, it is justifiable to recognize how the ASPs of Buenavista National High School achieved success as the Two-time First Runner-up Best Implementer in the entire division. Additionally, it is important to identify areas for improvement that are preventing the school from achieving the highest recognition in ASP implementation. There is hope that the various ASPs of the school can be benchmarked by other schools, finding the advantages to be beneficial in multiple ways.

Research Questions

This study was moving toward its primary objective of probing the successful implementation of the Adopt-a-School Program at Buenavista National High School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the practices of Buenavista National High School (BNHS) towards the implementation of the Adopt-a-School Program in the following phases?

1.1 Pre-Implementation

1.1.1 Root cause analysis

1.1.2 Approaches

1.1.3 Partners

1.1.4 Document of partnership

1.2 Implementation Proper

1.2.1 Varied resources

1.2.2 Documentation

1.2.3 Problems encountered

1.2.4 Progress monitoring

1.3 Post Implementation

1.3.1 Completion of the program

1.3.2 Significant role

1.3.3 Completion monitoring as stated in the IRR

1.3.4 Evaluation

2. In the course of the implementation of the ASP, what assistance was coming from the donors in support of the following areas?

- 2.1 Learning environment;
- 2.2 Learning support;
- 2.3 Technology support;
- 2.4 Health and nutrition;
- 2.5 Reading program;
- 2.6 Training and development;
- 2.7 Direct assistance; and
- 2.8 Assistive Learning Devices for Students with special needs
- 3. What are the effects of the Adopt-a-School Program on the school's performance?
 - 3.1 based on the perception of the participants; and
 - 3.1.1 efforts of the school through its ASPs
 - 3.1.2 ASPs addressed the problems
 - 3.1.3 emulation of BNHS' ASPs
 - 3.2 based on the School Report Card (SRC)
 - 3.2.1 decreased in drop-out
 - 3.2.2 increased in enrolment
 - 3.2.3 increased in participation rate of stakeholders
 - 3.2.4 doubled numbers in awards and recognition
 - 3.2.5 increasing sources of ASP funds
- 4. What are the keys to the successful implementation of Buenavista National High School's Adopt-a-School Programs?
 - 4.1 Collaboration of the community members
 - 4.2 Efforts of the proponent or organizer
 - 4.3 Accountability
- 5. From the success stories of the Adopt-a-School Program at Buenavista National High School, what Adopt-A-School Program could be benchmarked by other schools?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design in terms of methodology, research locale, research population and sample, research instrument, and data-gathering procedures.

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative research design, specifically the Transcendental Phenomenological Design through epoche, to explore the success stories of implementing the Adopt-a-School Programs at Buenavista National High School. This methodology is preferred because the researcher aims to capture the stories of the ASPs' program beneficiaries as they experienced becoming a part of these extended services of the school to its learners, family of the learners, stakeholders and other community members. According to Heotis (2020), phenomenology and hermeneutics, especially the philosophical ideas of Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger, form the foundation for phenomenological research methodologies. Husserl's central thesis is that one can investigate and describe the essential elements of one's experience while suspending

presuppositions to understand the essence of an event. On the other hand, the primary goal of choosing a phenomenological methodology was to encapsulate the entire meaning of the participants' experiences as shared in their own words.

The researcher deemed a phenomenological methodology appropriate for this study, as it allows others to understand the meaning participants attribute to their actions, including their thoughts, feelings, beliefs, values, and assumptive worlds. To understand the essence of the studied phenomenon, the researcher aimed to provide an accurate and vivid description of the lived experience (Neubauer et al., 2019). The researcher must understand the deeper perspectives captured through face-to-face interaction (Alhazmi and Kaufmann, 2022). Also, the researcher discussed the importance of understanding the participants' stories regarding implementation, experiences, and lessons acquired in the Adopt-a-School Program. Thus, when describing that experience, the researcher remains free from theoretical or social constructs.

To complete this study, the researcher—a Guidance Designate who is actively involved in every ASP at BNHS—applied the epoche method by bracketing preexisting beliefs, attitudes, and feelings. Heotis (2020) emphasized Moustakas' elaboration that the researcher should be open, receptive, and naive when listening to participants share their experiences with the phenomenon under investigation. Moreover, Alhazmi and Kaufmann, (2022) advised researchers to engage in this reflection throughout the study and to make explicit our understandings, beliefs, biases, and assumptions. The researcher bracketed the data, gave each statement equal weight, and elicited insignificant responses. The researcher grouped the participant responses into themes, which served as the foundation for a textural description of the phenomenon. Neubauer et al. (2019), emphasized phenomenological reflection and imaginative variation in constructing structural themes and characterizations from the textural meanings that go beyond the façade and into the essence of the experience. The researcher's final step involves synthesizing meaning and quality, combining all fundamental structural and textural descriptions into a single statement that captures the essence of the program's entire implementation.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the Buenavista District, specifically at Buenavista National High School (BNHS). This school is considered the most highly populated school in the district, with a total student population of 1502 for the school year 2022-2023, and it is expected to increase, with 63 teaching and non-teaching personnel per Plantilla.

The locale of the study was chosen because the school was awarded the 2021 and 2022 Brigada Eskwela Best Implementing School under the Mega School Category in the cluster and First Runner-Up in the division level by the Division Office for two consecutive years in the previous assessments of various schools with the implementation of the Adopt-a-School Program Brigada Eskwela.

Figure 2

Location Map of Buenavista National High School

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps/search/Buenavista+National+High+School,+Buenavista,+Marinduque/@13.2519266,121.9412918,14z/data=!3m1!4b1?entry=ttu>

Research Population and Sample

This study employed a purposive sampling technique in selecting the population. The beneficiaries of the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) implemented by BNHS in different categories over the previous five years were considered. These categories include Healing and Firming Families for a More Holistic Education (HAFFMHE), Annual Send-off Programs for Provincial Players, Annual Brigada Eskwela, Annual Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage, and Concreting of BNHS Grounds.

The number of respondents for the face-to-face interview was fourteen (14), chosen from various beneficiaries with direct involvement and first-hand information about the ASP programs of BNHS. For HAFFMHE, different types of respondents were selected to represent each beneficiary type, including separated parents, single parents, and orphans. For the Send-off Program for Players, respondents included a coach, a Sports Coordinator from past and present, a MIMAROPARAA player for two consecutive years, and a silver medalist provincial player. For the Forum on Teenage Pregnancy, respondents included a former student who attended the forum and later became a beauty queen in college, as well as a former student who attended the program and is now a mother. For the Concreting of the School Ground, respondents included the school head, the President of the PTA, the Alumni Association Treasurer, and the President of the Supreme Student Government when the project was implemented. For Brigada

Eskwela, both internal and external stakeholders were consulted. Internal stakeholders included the present principal, the BE Coordinator, and the ASP School Coordinator. External stakeholders included a church deacon representing their group and an officer from civic organizations.

Research Instrument

The researcher conducted structured, in-depth phenomenological interviews using a validated self-made questionnaire with the beneficiaries. Audio-video recording was utilized to better understand the interviewees' answers. The questions were directed toward the participants' experiences, feelings, beliefs, and convictions about BNHS' implementation of ASPs.

The interview guide questionnaire consists of the following parts: pre-implementation, implementation proper, post-implementation, assistance from donors to support ASP implementation, and effects of the project based on the perception of the participant.

The first part comprises pre-implementation questions, reflecting the procedures and preliminaries made by the different personalities involved before conducting the ASP. This includes the reason for the need to conduct the ASP, who was involved in identifying BNHS as the beneficiary school, what made the school qualified for the program, and the documents to confirm the transactions between the beneficiaries and the sponsors.

The subsequent section covers implementation questions, addressing the procedures for accomplishing the ASP. These questions encompass the sufficiency of supplies for the project, the problems encountered, and the remedies or precautions taken by the implementing bodies during the implementation, as well as the documents and procedures used to track the progress of the program being implemented.

The following set of questions pertains to post-implementation, measuring the effectiveness of the project implementation according to the adherence of the implementing bodies to the department's protocol. This part includes sharing the interviewees' experiences of being part of the ASP, their perceived importance of their role in implementing the ASP, and the procedures and documents used in monitoring the projects.

After the questions on the different phases of the project's implementation, the confirmation of the common forms of assistance provided to the school in accomplishing the ASPs was identified and validated. The sufficiency of the assistance was measured, and interventions were made if problems were encountered with regards to the supplies.

Finally, the last part of the interview guide determined the beneficiaries' perceptions of the effects of the project on their lives. This included the realizations they had after benefiting from or engaging in accomplishing the programs, the factors that, for them,

contributed to the success of the project, and their beliefs or confirmation that the ASPs must be implemented by other schools.

Data Gathering Procedures

In gathering the data for this study, the researcher followed the primary steps outlined below:

First, the researcher requested an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. This endorsement was then forwarded to the principal of BNHS for approval. The content of the research study underwent assessment and evaluation until permission was granted. It was ensured that no government funds would be used during the activity in accordance with DepEd Order No. 9 Series of 2005. Classes were not disrupted, and proper coordination with the school administrators was arranged before the conduct of the activity.

Triangulation was utilized, incorporating interviews, observations, and document analysis. Face-to-face interviews played a crucial role in collecting in-depth information about the successful implementation of the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) at Buenavista National High School, eliciting the perceptions and descriptions of the participants' experiences.

Although success stories could be investigated through observation, shared interactions, and literature, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with open-ended questions with the participants. The researcher engaged directly with the participants, posing a few open-ended questions using a validated self-structured questionnaire to ultimately understand the respondents' stories. Audio recordings were utilized with their permission to fully evaluate and comprehend the interviewees' statements regarding the ASP of BNHS.

Furthermore, observational notes regarding the participants' techniques for recounting their experiences, behavior during the interview, and similar information were utilized as supplementary data. Positive outcomes of the ASPs were even observed based on their way of life and responses that reflected the outcomes of the ASP in their personal development.

To provide a figurative justification for the successful implementation of the ASP in BNHS, data related to the different projects implemented in the previous five years was obtained from the respective offices. This included the total number of beneficiaries for each project, the total number of volunteers, the total number of consistent donors, the total cash amount incurred, the total amount of goods in cash, the total number of Deeds of

donations executed, and the total number of MOAs signed. These data were presented through tabular presentations and graphs.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In presenting the findings of the study, a thematic analysis framework was utilized since the study focused on the experiences of the respondents. This method was chosen due to its constant-comparative nature, involving systematic reading and re-reading of transcripts (Braun et al., 2019). The thematic analysis process was conducted systematically to ensure the quality of the final product. Whether this was applied to interviews or focus groups, is based on the premise that participants' memories are valuable for inquiry, synthesis, and in-depth description of their experiences. This approach assumes that information recorded in documents or other artifacts accurately reflects reality at the time it was created and should be treated with the same level of confidence as participant-spoken memories. Lochmiller (2021) emphasized the importance of the researcher's interpretation of recorded data from participants or found in documents as compelling. The researcher followed similar procedures by conducting interviews with open-ended questions and analyzing data from documents related to the ASPs.

Lochmiller described the analysis process involving three phases: setup, analysis, and interpretation. The credibility and trustworthiness of the reported information must be highly regarded to conduct thematic analysis. No alterations or substitutions were made to the respondents' statements, who were beneficiaries of various ASPs at BNHS. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' experiences and feelings, a tabular presentation of statements is included in Chapter Four.

This procedure involves organizing the dataset for analysis, including transcribing identifying references from audio and video sources along with handwritten field notes. Bracketing the researcher's beliefs about the successful implementation of ASPs in BNHS ensured the integrity of the analysis.

After bracketing, the focus shifted to intuition, with an emphasis on attributing meaning to the phenomenon. Grouping invariant horizons into themes allowed for a composite description of the essence of all participants' stories. This description served as the core of the ASP success story at the school, potentially useful for benchmarking activities by other schools.

Data analysis followed, with coding and categorizing to make sense of the significant meaning of the phenomenon. Greening (2019) described this as the third step in the phenomenological process, involving analyzing and describing the data. The researcher persistently worked with detailed data to emerge essences and themes from respondents' statements, striving for a thorough description of the phenomenon.

Participants' quotes were included for vivid and convincing findings description, with all responses given equal value and non-overlapping, non-repetitive statements listed. Through taking notes, the participants behavior was used for digesting information that is

applied in their actual daily lives after their experiences with the ASPs of the school. As a result, this helped with long-term, in-the-moment mental processes by facilitating the coding of information, which relieves mnemonic processes and aids in the creation of the answer. Data from documents were presented through graphs, tables and figures, with comparisons made for a more detailed description of events. Line graphs depicted movement, change, and trends in support for the ASP project.

Finally, the social significance of the findings was emphasized, describing the positive effects experienced by beneficiaries and validating the benchmarking of projects.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the statistical data relative to the problems posited. The corresponding analyses and interpretations of the data were incorporated into this chapter.

The first section discusses Buenavista National High School practices in implementing Adopt-a-School Programs, followed by an examination of the common forms of assistance provided to the school. It explores the effects of the ASPs on the school's performance, as perceived by beneficiaries and reflected in the School Report Card data. The latter part of the chapter delves into ASPs and practices that could serve as benchmarks for other schools.

Emerging themes, based on participants' accounts of the entire process justifying the successful implementation, are supported by documents vividly detailing each project and phase. Various graphs, tables and figures are presented for each project to assess implementation success visually. Additionally, narratives of participants and beneficiaries of the projects are included, complementing the data to complete the triangulation process of analysis.

For every challenge concerning learners, the school implements intervention programs through ASPs. Similarly, in the execution of various Adopt-a-School Program, Buenavista National High School endeavors to make a difference to achieve the objectives of each ASP launched. The entire process typically comprises three stages: pre-implementation, implementation, and post-implementation.

Practices of Buenavista National High School Towards the Implementation of Adopt-A-School Program

The very first phase of any school program or project is very crucial. This will determine the success or failure of the objective set by the ASP. It is an essential preparatory process that aims to collect information and requirements. The primary goal is to justify the need for conducting the ASP and how to successfully carry out the objectives of the program.

Pre-implementation Phase

The pre-implementation stage conceptualized the various projects that justified the requirements to implement the proposed project. This stage comprises of the root-cause analysis, the partner agencies that supported the school, the various civic organizations, other stakeholders, reasons for selecting BNHS as a recipient of the program, people involved in the selection of BNHS as a beneficiary, and the signing of the MOA. Likewise, in this stage the different forms used in each part of the phase were taken into consideration, scrutinized and analyzed as a requirement and an attachment that could justify the implementation of the specified phase of implementation.

The various ASPs stated herein were formulated based on the needs of the learners, as stated by Harrington and De Bruler (2019), who said that student-centered learning is an educational philosophy or approach to learning that places students' needs and interests at the forefront of the operations and decision-making of a school or district. Added hereto is the concrete support of the various components of the community in the implementation of each ASP. Astbury (2022) emphasized that, in the end, schools will attain more effective primary output delivery over a longer period by forging deeper and more positive ties with stakeholders—both locally and nationally. This reiterates that stakeholders play a big role in the success of each project in the school that has effects on the educational outcomes of the learners.

Table 1 presents the Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National High School and their beneficiaries.

Table 1

Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National High School and Their Beneficiaries

Adopt-a-School Program	Total No. of Beneficiaries
HAFFMHE	215
Send-off Programs for Players	220 varies annually
Forum on Teen-age Pregnancy and Early Marriage	400 Varies according to the annual enrollment
Concreting of BNHS Ground	1500 School Population, Stakeholders, Teachers
Brigada Eskwela	Varies according to annual enrollment

Source: Junior and Senior High School Guidance Offices of Buenavista National High School

The different ASPs cited in Table 1 underwent data gathering and root-cause analysis to justify the needs for their implementation. as stated by the implementing authorities.

ASPs cited have varied numbers of beneficiaries. Among these are the Send Off Program for Players, Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage, and Brigada Eskwela.

The number of beneficiaries for Brigada Eskwela and the Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage varies according to the school enrollment, same with Send Off Program for Players.

Figure 3, "Beneficiaries of Healing and Firming for a More Holistic Education," shows the percentage of beneficiaries.

Figure 3

Beneficiaries of Healing and Firming for a More Holistic Education

Legend:

- Orphaned students
- Students with solo parent
- Students with separated parents

Sources: Junior High School and Senior High School Guidance Offices

In the pie graph the greatest percentage of the program's beneficiaries are students with a single parent; with a total number of 163 students out of the 215 beneficiaries. Additionally, the program included 46 students with separated parents and six orphaned students. The total number of beneficiaries was 14.33% of the total student population. The project was spearheaded by the Senior High School Guidance Office with the coordination of the SHS Coordinator.

For the annual Send Off Program for Players, the number of beneficiaries varies according to the events the players will compete in at the provincial meet. This program includes the coaches and all members of the delegation. Previously, beneficiaries were

from different secondary schools in the district, but in the recent program, it included both elementary and secondary schools in the entire district, due to a strong request from the district supervisor. This is another proposed annual program by the Guidance Office.

The Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage ASP varies in the number of beneficiaries according to the school's annual enrolment. This is an annual ASP of the school in coordination with the Population Commission through the Buenavista Teen Center and the Guidance Office.

The ASP for Concreting of the School Grounds benefits the entire school population, including internal and external stakeholders. This project provides lasting services that can be enjoyed by various components of the educational system if the school continues to serve the community. The program was initiated by a former school head in cooperation with the Brigada Eskwela implementing bodies.

Since Brigada Eskwela is now a year-round ASP, a greater population benefits from its provisions. This initiative incorporates various other ASPs of the school, involving different implementing bodies, offices, organizations, and stakeholders.

The school always considers the urgency of the ASPs' implementation, the number of beneficiaries, and the positive outcomes that the project may bring to the lives of the beneficiaries. This means all aspects of the learning process and members of the community are considered before confirming the ASP's implementation.

Data in Table 2 are the interviewees' responses during the face-to-face interview about the pre-implementation stage of the ASPs.

Table 2

Pre-implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School Program in Terms of Root Cause Analysis

Theme	Definition	Responses
1. Convened	Referring to the attendance of the concern individuals during the root-cause analysis upon identification of the problem	<p><i>"Naga-root-cause analysis. Ang mga involve ay ako, Physical Facilities Coordinator, MDRRM School Coordinator, Barangay Councilor, SSG President, Teacher's Association President etc. May data kitang hawak from the identified problems at ito ay mga totoong data. Genuine data." - The Present Principal</i></p> <p><i>"Opp. Naga convene lahat ng committees ng school before ang actual Brigada Eskwela para I-analyze yung mga needs ng school at paano nag- arise ang ganong needs." - BE School Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>"Mayroon. Bumabaha sa campus. Ayaw padaanin ang kanal sa central school. Sa barangay naman ay, yung dinadaan ay subdivision. Hindi pwedeng gastusan ng barangay kasi no public fund sa pwedeng gamitin sa private entity." - Former Gen. PTA President of BNHS</i></p>

		<i>"May root-cause analysis with Mr. Lining. Nilapit sa mga teachers sa meeting. Nilapit din sa PTA, LGU and Alumni. Supplementary materials lang sa PTA, Barangay at mga students. Kung meron limited</i>
2. Convened	Referring to the attendance of the concern individuals during the root-cause analysis upon identification of the problem	<i>"Walang share ang SSG. Alumni ang main partner, the labor, and materials ay galing sa kanila. Even the planning ay sa Alumni, through Engr. Arvin Siena." - Former BNHS TIC (Concreting of School Ground</i>
3. Absence	Concerned person failed to attend the root-cause analysis	<i>"Wala po akong na-attendan na meeting noon. Basta po ang unang-unang recall ko ng project, prinoposed ko po sya ay way back before 'nung ako pa lang po ay Grade 10, humangad po ako bilang President. Prinesent, prinoposed ko po 'nung debate. After po nun ay wala na po akong natatandaan na meeting of some sort about the project." - Former SSG President (Concreting of School Ground)</i>

Theme	Definition	Responses
		<i>"Walang root-cause analysis. Originally ang plano ay bibili ng lote. Konti ang nakalap ng pondo. Nasa three hundred thousand lang ang pondo. Kulang para sa school lot dahil 1.5 milyon halos ang halaga ng lote. Hanggang nakapag-decision na pagandahin na lang yung school ground o yung school? Hanggang hindi na rin nangyari dahil nag-usap na sila ni Ma'am Saporna about sa maputik na ground ng school. Tapos sabi ni President, why not ipa-semento na lang yung ground laanan ng pondo." - Alumni Treasurer (Concreting of School Ground)</i>
4. Attendance not required	Presence of the person for the stage is unnecessary	<i>"Hindi po ako kasama sa root-cause analysis. Papasok lang po ako kapag may donation na." - ASP School Coordinator</i>

The participants, who were the beneficiaries of the ASPs, justified that consultations were held by the various committees involved before implementing the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) at Buenavista National High School (BNHS). This is anchored to DepEd Order No. 026, series 2022 titled Implementing Guidelines on the Establishment of School Governance Council, the School-Based Management (SBM) supports the participation of stakeholders, equips the local community to own the decisions taken, and encourages the growth of current networks in the schools. In these, include root-cause analysis as part of the BNHS' SBM Team.

It has been confirmed by the BNHS principal that a root cause analysis was done. *"Naga-root-cause analysis."*

It was also reiterated in the statement of the School BE Coordinator. *"Opo. Naga convene lahat ng committees ng school."*

When the various ASPs started to implement them, even the former PTA agreed that root cause analysis was being done. He mentioned one of the analyses:

“Bumabaha sa campus. Ayaw padaanin ang kanal sa central school. Sa barangay naman ay, yung dinadaan ay subdivision. “Hindi pwedeng gastusan ng barangay kasi no public fund sa pwedeng gamitin sa private entity.”

Similarly, the Resource Gap Analysis Tool of ASP, prescribed by DepEd in implementing ASP which was stated in the IRR, was used to confirm that there is a need for a program due to the lack of funds. According to the principal, it usually involves the principal, physical facilities coordinator, SMDRRM coordinator, Faculty, PTA, SSG, Alumni officers, Barangay officials, and stakeholders.

Table 3 contains the data gathered related to the ASP Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage Cases in Buenavista National High School.

Table 3

Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage Cases in Buenavista National High School from School Year 2018- 2019 to School Year 2021-2022

School Year	Teenage Pregnancy		Early Marriage		Total
	JHS	SHS	JHS	SHS	
2021- 2022	3	0	0	0	3
2020 - 2021	1	0	0	2	3
2019 - 2020	0	2	0	0	2
2018 - 2019	1	5	0	0	6
TOTAL	5	7	0	2	14

Source: Junior High School and Senior High School Guidance Offices of Buenavista NHS

Prior to the conduct of the ASP, data were gathered relative to the emerging problems that hinder the learning of the students. The urgency of conducting the project was evident due to the increasing number of teenage pregnancies both in the junior high school and in the senior high school. In the School Year 2018-2019, most of the cases of teenage pregnancy involved the senior high school students with five cases and one case in the junior high school. These figures made the offices concerned to conduct the ASP.

After the initial conduct of the ASP in the following school year, School Year 2019-2020, the cases somehow dropped to 40% in the senior high school with two cases and a zero case in the junior high school. In the following school year, a zero case in teenage pregnancy was achieved by the senior high school with a one case in the junior high school. In the school year 2021-2022, the cases in the junior high school gradually increased thrice the case in 2020-2021 which is one while the senior high school maintained its zero case in teenage pregnancy.

On the other hand, early marriage cases among students were rare aside from the two cases in the senior high school in the school year 2020-2021. This could be attributed to

the minor ages of the students in the junior high school. The couple cannot be married although they lived together as a family.

The documents collected confirmed that the school consistently employs RCA because the members of the School-Based Management (SBM) team believe in its effectiveness. One key advantage of RCA is that it enables teams to take appropriate actions to correct issues and prevent their recurrence, resulting in fewer errors and less rework (TechArcis, 2021).

However, there were instances when some officers did not attend or were not informed about the consultations, even though implementing an ASP at BNHS requires the involvement and engagement of most stakeholders.

One such instance was highlighted by the SSG President, who stated: *“Wala po akong na-attendan na meeting noon...”*

The SSG Adviser, a faculty member, represented the SSG President. Another officer who did not attend in one of the root cause analyses was the Alumni Treasurer. She said during the interview that:

“Walang root-cause analysis. Originally ang plano ay bibili ng lote.”

This is because only their alumni president was consulted. Nevertheless, after the consultation, the body was immediately informed about the plan regarding the problem relayed by the teacher-in-charge.

Another key implementer who did not attend the consultations was the ASP School Coordinator.

“Hindi po ako kasama sa root-cause analysis...”

She was informed regarding the problem during faculty meetings, as stated by the former TIC of BNHS.

“May root-cause analysis with the BE School Coordinator...”

The Department of Education emphasized that root cause analysis is necessary to unravel the ultimate source of the problem as stated in Section F, Roles and Responsibilities of All SGC Members of DepEd Order No. 026 Series of 2022, pursuant to the Governance of Education Act of 2001.

The latter was not observed in some circumstances based on the statements of the SSG President and the ASP Coordinator of the School though most of the key personalities were able to represent their offices in every root-cause analysis.

Table 4 below contains the statements of the respondents regarding the different partner agencies of BNHS that supported the school’s ASPs.

Table 4

Pre-implementation Phase of ASP in Terms of Partner Agency Who Supported the School as One of the Approaches of Buenavista National High School

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Volunteerism	The act of involving themselves voluntarily as a group or individual in accomplishing ASPs of BNHS without further notice	<p><i>“Madami. Unang-una na ang PNP, BFP, LGU at Municipal Government Unit, Eagles, Akrho, Tau Gamma, Iglesia Ni Cristo, Marinduque Riders Club, mga private business owners, public individuals, Senior Citizen, Alumni, Kuya Kuy’s Adventures, FCB, Office of the Vice-Governor, Casa John.” - BNHS’ Present principal</i></p>
2. No Partner Agency	The ASP was solely accomplished by one body or organization of stakeholders	<p><i>“Mga group of fraternities ay willing mag-render ng service like Akrho, Tau Gamma, Religious Group INC, Eagles, Riders Marinduque Club. Usually ay labor and assistance. Minsan school supplies pag maigi siguro ang budget.” - BE School Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Alumni. They preferred to give back something to their alma mater. Nag pledge ang mga batches through the initiatives of the Alumni President. Nakikita ko duon na they love the school, whatever is good for the school, whatever is good for the student’s parang that certain goal. Na ganito ang pagtingin ko sa school. Ganito ang ambag ng BNHS sa akin. Kung tutuusin it is not just thousands but hundred thousand.” - Former BNHS’ TIC</i></p> <p><i>“Ang mostly po na nakikita ko nung naga implement na ay LGU. May engineer na present, Engr. Reynan Siena, Alumni President, Engr. Arvin Siena. Wala po akong nakitang PTA President nun.” - Former SSG President</i></p> <p><i>“Walang ka partner agency ang alumni. Pero yung first part yata nung concrete ground ay sa PTA nun. Meron din daw share ang teachers at the classroom.” - Alumni Treasurer</i></p> <p><i>“First part of the concreting of the school ground, walang partner agencies. Nagbenta ng t-shirt for seventy-five pesos, twenty-five pesos ay napunta for the concreting. Apat na quadrants, one for each year level. First year muna, naghati-hati sa paggawa ng ground. Ang labor ay through volunteerism. Walang counterpart ang alumni sa first part of the project.” - Former PTA President</i></p>

In the pre-implementation phase of the Alternative Learning System Program (ASP) at Buenavista National High School (BNHS), it is common for partner agencies such as the Philippine National Police (PNP), Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP), Local Government Unit (LGU), and Municipal Government Unit (MGU) to be involved. This aligns closely with Section 2 of Republic Act No. 9418, also known as The Bayanihang Bayan Program (BBP), which aims to institutionalize strategies for rural development and strengthen volunteerism, emphasizing the participation of various sectors in public and civic affairs. This consistent involvement of government agencies may be attributed to their awareness of BBP and their commitment to participating in school activities, particularly during Brigada Eskwela. Such engagement aligns with their obligations under the Results-Based Performance Management System (RBPMS), specifically in terms of community and inter-agency linkages, as mandated for government employees.

In addition to government volunteers, several civil society organizations and private sectors frequently contribute to the ASPs at BNHS. These include The Pathway, Akrho, Tau Gamma, Riders Club of Marinduque, Kuya Kuy's Adventure, Senior Citizens Association of Buenavista, and Iglesia Ni Cristo, among others.

The principal said that:

“Mga group of fraternities ay willing mag-render ng service.”

Along with these volunteers, the Alumni, PTA, and SSG are always present and supportive of the school's programs and projects. The former TIC said that:

“Alumni. They preferred to give back something to their alma mater. Nag pledged ang mga batches through the initiatives of the Alumni President.”

Alumni played a significant role in supporting Buenavista National High School (BNHS), particularly during the concreting of the school grounds, showcasing the valuable assistance alumni can offer. Jotform Education (2021) underscores the potential for graduates to contribute financially and otherwise as they progress in their careers, suggesting that school administrators should strategize ways to leverage alumni resources effectively. This involvement of alumni was prominently observed in the Alternative Learning System Programs (ASP) at BNHS, where alumni members extended various forms of assistance to the school to ensure the successful completion of projects.

Mourya (2021) highlights the importance of specific leadership approaches when working with volunteers in non-profit organizations, emphasizing the need to cultivate enthusiasm and motivation as volunteers are not monetarily compensated. Aranda (2019) supports this assertion, noting that different motivations for volunteering can impact outcomes differently, with self-determined motivations leading to better health and lower burnout rates among volunteers compared to those with control motivations.

The ASPs at BNHS greatly relied on volunteerism, involving groups, organizations, and individuals in service provision. The collective participation of various stakeholders significantly contributed to the success of each ASP. BNHS well-established connection with its parents, stakeholders and community members greatly contributes to achieving

every set goal, endeavor and ASP. While one respondent noted the absence of partner agencies in supporting a Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) initiative, it underscores the immediate partnership between the school and parents' organization in addressing school needs.

Table 5 presents the school year with equivalent forms of assistance and services extended to the school with monetary equivalent, and number of partners or volunteers.

Table 5

Buenavista National High School Brigada Eskwelas' Forms of Assistance and Service with Monetary Equivalent and Number of Partners from School Year 2019-2020 to School Year 2021-2022

SCHOOL YEAR	FORMS OF ASSISTANCE	MONETARY EQUIVALENT	NO. OF PARTNERS
2021- 2022	Generated Resources		
	>Assistance to Learners	3, 950. 00	
	>Assistance to Teachers	21, 850.00	
	>Assistance to School	55, 220.00	
	Subtotal 1	81, 020.00	
	Volunteer Services and Value-Added Activities	1, 6697, 481.26	
	DRRM Implementation	9, 000. 00	
	Community Home Partnership	239, 040.00	
	WinS	0.00	
	Brigada Pagbasa	270, 000.00	
	GRAND TOTAL	2, 296, 541.26	129
SCHOOL YEAR	FORMS OF ASSISTANCE	MONETARY EQUIVALENT	NO. OF PARTNERS
2020-2021	Generated Resources		
	>Assistance to Learners	61, 795.00	
	>Assistance to Teachers	135.00	
	>Assistance to School	65, 060.00	
	Subtotal 1	126, 990.00	
	Volunteer Services and Value-Added Activities	29, 027.63	
	DRRM Implementation	9, 000. 00	
	Community Home Partnership	545, 000.00	
	WinS	16, 000.00	
	Brigada Pagbasa	97, 650.00	
	GRAND TOTAL	823, 667.63	52
2019-2020	GRAND TOTAL	871, 210.00	47
2018-2019	GRAND TOTAL	65, 015.00	29

*Latest 2 school years are in a more detailed presentation to justify the award received of the school

*Later years of ASPs implementation were not uploaded due to the unavailability of the ASP database

Sources: Brigada Eskwela Summary of Donations - Office of the Principal, Brigada Eskwela Database of BNHS, ASP School Coordinator

The data clearly demonstrate the increasing number of volunteers over the past four years of implementing the program. These indicate a steady rise each year: 2019 recorded 29 partners, 2020 saw 47 partners, 2021 reported 59 partners, and 2022 documented 129 partners. These figures underscore the enduring bond between the school and its community and stakeholders.

Paraiso (2022) emphasizes the positive impact of community involvement on academic achievement and school improvement, noting that collaboration among families, communities, and schools fosters student encouragement, participation in advanced programs, and improved attendance. This involvement is key to addressing school-related challenges, fostering strong partnerships, and mitigating dropout rates.

The progressive increase in the number of Brigada Eskwela partners and the corresponding monetary contributions each year reflects the unwavering support of BNHS stakeholders. Furthermore, statements from volunteers representing various organizations, partner agencies, and other stakeholders affirm the full support of the community towards the school's Alternative Learning System Programs (ASPs). The concurrent rise in volunteer numbers and monetary assistance, underscores the coordinated efforts and strong support from community members for the benefit of learners and the school.

In Table 6 presented are the approaches that made BNHS the beneficiary school of the volunteers for the ASP.

Table 6

Pre-implementation Phase of the Adopt-a-School Program in Terms of Approaches for Selecting the School as a Partner for the Program

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Sense of Connection and Strong Partnership	Strong connection between BNHS and its stakeholders Involving the stakeholders in the process of planning, implementing, and accomplishing an ASP for BNHS	<p><i>“Sa palagay ko ay dahil sa open communication sa kanila. Pangalawa ay transparency, yung nakikita nila kung saan napupunta yung inabigay nila. Another ay accountability, yung properly accounted ang donations nila. May report tayo. Strong partnership, yung nakikita nila, kung paano kita mag-reach out sa kanila; ako ang gadala ng sulat. Kung hindi makapunta ay inatawagan ko sila. Yung ramdam nila na kailangan natin sila. Aside dun sa nakikita nila ang needs ng school.” - Present Principal</i></p> <p><i>“Siguro po dahil sa pangangailangan ng mga bata. Bago pa kami pumalaot sa mas malawak na programa na wala naman kaming pondo, why not ito na ang pagawa dahil ito na ang kailangan. Maliban sa may nagawa na tayo ay ito talaga ang kailangan.” - Alumni Treasurer</i></p> <p><i>“Karamihan po sa myembro nila, ng mga grupo ay alumni ng BNHS. Dahil siguro rin ay nabibigyan sila ng recognition. May mga certificates po na ina-issue ang school</i></p>

natin para marecognize ang effort nila.” - School BE Coordinator

“Karamihan ay alumni ang members or employees nila kaya alam ang pangangailangan ng school. Dahil din siguro nasa bayan tayo at malapit, magandang puntahan.” - School ASP Coordinator

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
2. Alternative way	Internal stakeholder's another approach of realizing a project	<i>“Maganda naman ang adhikain natin at kung tutuusin ang mga t-shirt natin ay maganda naman at mura.” - Former PTA President</i>

The strong connection between Buenavista National High School (BNHS) and its alumni, stakeholders, and community members community is very evident with the statements of the beneficiaries in Table 6. This made them decide to make BNHS the recipient of their services and led them to select BNHS as the recipient of their services and projects. According to Giving Compass (2022), volunteers have the freedom to choose how they support the school for the benefit of its students and the institution. This motivates volunteers to actively participate in every Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) at BNHS. Alumni and stakeholders, regardless of their affiliations with various organizations, offices, or companies, strive to contribute and ensure the success of every ASP, providing motivation, hope, and resilience (Giving Compass, 2022).

As revealed in the statements of respondents in Table 6, the alumni treasurer shared the rationale behind their full support for concreting the school grounds, despite having other plans for the organization's funds. There was a sense of urgency regarding the project, which was deemed essential for the benefit of the learners. Regardless of their preference, the needs of the school are their priority.

“Siguro po dahil sa pangangailangan ng mga bata. Bago pa kami pumalaot sa mas malawak na programa na wala naman kaming pondo, why not ito na ang pagawa dahil ito na ang kailangan...”

According to Jotform Education (2021), alumni can support their alma mater in various ways, including reconnecting with current students and devising strategies to aid the school in achieving success in all its endeavors. This phenomenon is evident not only in Buenavista National High School (BNHS) but also in numerous other educational institutions.

Two respondents highlighted that most members in volunteer organizations are BNHS alumni. As such, they possess a strong sense of voluntary engagement in addressing the needs of BNHS.

The ASP Coordinator of the school has faith with the alumni members.

“Karamihan ay alumni ang members or employees nila kaya alam ang pangangailangan ng school.”

Same statement was uttered by the School BE Coordinator, *“Karamihan po sa myembro nila, ng mga grupo ay alumni ng BNHS.”*

On the other hand, the present school head of BNHS believes that not only open communication plays a vital role in making the school a recipient of programs but also transparency.

“Sa palagay ko ay dahil sa open communication sa kanila. Pangalawa ay transparency, yung nakikita nila kung saan napupunta yung inabigay nila ...”

Another important aspect was the proper financial reporting of most projects and the personal connection with the stakeholders. An action that can be made possible by exhibiting moral principles in the management of finances, such as being truthful, reliable, and possessing a high degree of integrity when acquiring, allocating, using, analyzing, and reporting on school finances (Bhoke, 2021).

“Another ay accountability, yung properly accounted ang donations nila. May report tayo...”

Buenavista National High School (BNHS) employs various approaches to promote ongoing projects and encourage support and participation from the community. However, personal connections and proactive efforts to engage with the community foster strong bonds and partnerships. Personalizing communication somehow bonds the school to its stakeholders and advances volunteering for school needs. Volunteers are often motivated by a sense of volunteerism when inquiring about participating in Brigada Eskwela (BE) initiatives. Some organizations and volunteers await the school's invitation or request for their services. Upon notification, whether orally or in writing, they mobilize their resources, exemplified by the solidarity demonstrated by the Iglesia ni Cristo brethren, who unite as one body to contribute. Likewise, most of the organizations and brotherhoods in the community or where alumni are members are one call away in every ASP of the school.

BNHS also maintains connections with stakeholders through various channels, including a community radio station named Radyo Kamalindig, the school's Facebook page managed in coordination with the Division Office, and Messenger. Radyo Kamalindig serves as a platform to disseminate information about school activities to the public. The stakeholders and community members are constantly updated to the whereabouts of the school through this Chanel. With regards to social platforms, at present, the school's Facebook page boasts nearly 4,240 followers, with posts reaching approximately 14,127 individuals and garnering 5,716 engagements. These platforms serve as effective means of informing volunteers about the ASPs conducted by the school. Because of the easiest way of connecting with others through the technology, its vast scope contributes to the feasibility of every program launched.

These different approaches employed by Buenavista National High School in the implementation of the school's ASPs truly get the support of the different stakeholders. Aside from the established credibility of the school after serving the community for more than fifty years, the school has non-stop and varied ways on how to continuously get hold of the connection with its immediate support system members. The school sees to it that the involvement of stakeholders in every endeavor is present. This factor is the strongest tie that binds the school to its serving community.

In Table 7, statements of the participants indicate who was involved or what made BNHS the beneficiary of the Adopt-a-School Program. This emphasizes volunteering as the main factor of involvement.

Table 7

Pre-implementation Phase of ASP in Terms of Partners Involved in the Selection of BNHS as Beneficiary

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Volunteerism	Volunteers and decide to render their services to BNHS in the implementation of the ASPs	<p><i>“Usually ay sila na ang naga-offer ng services once na malaman nila na naga-start na ang Brigada Eskwela. Dun nakikita yung volunteerism talaga. Sa marketing strategy natin na pag-ere sa Radyo Kamalindig at sa Fb account natin nalalaman nila dahil may access sila. Yung malalapit binibigyna ng letters.”</i> - School BE Coordinator</p> <p><i>“Alumni at PTA ang nagakusang nagawa. Yan ‘yung SBM. Katulad nung Teachers’ Day, sila na ang nagkusa, ababa mo na sa kanila, sa stakeholders ang operations. Kusa na silang nalapit. LGU and MLGU din kusangnalapit. Eagles din ay nagakusa. Example ay yung clothes for a section of students. Private donors.”</i> - Present Principal</p> <p><i>“Private company, organization of the Siena Brothers.”</i> - Former TIC</p>
2. Stakeholders Choice	Initiative of the stakeholders and volunteers to choose the school they would be rendering their service	<p><i>“Endorsed ng destinado, pinagtibay ng Tagapangasiwa.”</i> - INC Deacon</p> <p><i>“May body po ang municipal council. So, halimbawa ay ang maga render ng service lamang ay buong municipal council, ang maga-organize, ang ga validate po kung saan sila maga ano ay yung council chairman.”</i> - Regent for Alumni Affairs Tau Gamma Phi Provincial Council</p> <p><i>“Sila ang nagde-decide (Chairman ng alumni and other officers) ibinababa na lang sa amin.”</i> - Alumni Treasurer</p>

Volunteering encompasses various terms across languages, yet its essence remains relatively simple to understand in English. According to Mourya (2021), volunteering involves individuals dedicating their free time to assist others, whether informally within communities or formally through organized efforts by institutions. The decision to

volunteer should always be left to the individual. Similarly, Muller (2018) defines volunteering as the provision of services without monetary compensation, emphasizing that it is a voluntary act and not obligatory. Those who volunteer extend assistance to others, beyond their immediate family or relatives, as highlighted in the work of DepEd ASP Toolkit Procedures.

In the Department of Education (DepEd) ASP Toolkit Procedures for Participation in the Adopt-a-School Program, adopting private entities have the freedom to select the school, region, and focus area for their efforts. The Adopt-a-School Program Secretariat maintains a list of priority schools and their specific needs to assist private businesses in their selection process.

During the pre-implementation phase, most respondents at BNHS concur that immediate partners and volunteers typically engage with schools upon learning about ASP or Brigada Eskwela through various project promotion strategies.

The School BE Coordinator states that:

“Usually ay sila na ang naga-offer ng services once na malaman nila na naga-start na ang Brigada Eskwela.”

They provide this service to the BNHS every year. The principal confidently added during the interview.

“Alumni at PTA ang nagakusang nagawa. Yan ‘yung SBM”

Khan (2020) placed emphasis on the vital role of parents in promoting school-community relationships. He stressed that it works as a link between school and community. Moreover, he pointed out that parental involvement in constructive areas proved positive for schools. The active participation of the PTA Officers and every parent truly helps to make others move and do their parts as components of the education circle.

On the other hand, other organization leaders coordinated with the school personnel and informed the members once their participation was confirmed.

“Sila ang nagde-decide (Chairman ng alumni and other officers of the brotherhood) ibinababa na lang sa amin.”

Another volunteer organization is the Iglesia Ni Cristo (INC). According to the interviewed deacon, they usually wait for the final decision of their leader in the provincial district office, which is coordinated with the church leader in the area.

“Endorsed ng destinado, pinagtibay ng Tagapangasiwa.”

While volunteer groups may formally secure requests from schools for documentation purposes, their primary objective is to actively participate in the school's projects. This demonstrates their willingness to contribute and respond to the school's needs, as highlighted by Republic Act No. 9418, also known as the Volunteer Act of 2007. This legislation institutionalizes strategies for rural development, strengthens volunteerism, and promotes corporate social responsibility by providing time, expertise, and services to recipient schools.

Becoming involved in Buenavista National High School's (BNHS) initiatives, regardless of the form of assistance, motivates volunteers and stakeholders to work towards the successful completion of projects launched by the school or initiated by stakeholders for the benefit of students. Aranda (2019) identified several variables—such as values, knowledge, self-esteem improvement, social aspects, and fulfilment of functions—as key predictors of satisfaction with volunteering.

Table 8 presents statements from respondents regarding the circumstances under which the Memorandum of Agreement should be utilized in the implementation of the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP).

Table 8

Pre-implementation Phase of ASP in Terms of Execution of Memorandum of Agreement and Kick-Off Program

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. No MOA	MOA means the Memorandum of Agreement expected to be executed by both parties, the recipient and the donor, endorsing the program by the sponsor or donor to Buenavista National High School with agreed duties and responsibilities for the consistent functionality of the project or ASP.	<p><i>“Wala pong MOA na pinipirmahan.”</i> - Present Principal</p> <p><i>“Wala pong MOA ang Send-off Program for Players and Teenage Pregnancy dahil mga short term ASPs ito.”</i> - ASP Coordinator</p> <p><i>“Wala pong opening ceremony at MOA.”</i> - Former SSG President</p> <p><i>“Wala pong MOA. Hindi ang ko aware na may MOA before. May financial report na pinasa for reporting sa school as a form of donation from the Alumni.”</i> - Former TIC</p>
2. No Opening due to Pandemic	Opening program or Kick-off was not observed because of pandemic.	<i>“Walang opening ceremony dahil sa Covid19.”</i> - Former PTA President
3. With Kick-off	<p>Kick-off program is the opening program of an ASP like Brigada Eskwela</p> <p>Kick-off program was observed based on the statements of the respondents.</p>	<p><i>“May opening or kick-off program ang Brigada Eskwela.”</i> - Present Principal</p> <p><i>“With kick-off ceremony kapag Brigada Eskwela”</i> - ASP Coordinator</p> <p><i>“May kick-off program. May attendance.”</i> - BE Coordinator</p> <p><i>“May kick-off program ang Brigada Eskwela. Nakaka-attend po kami.”</i> - INC Deacon</p> <p><i>“May kick-off ang Brigada Eskwela. Umaattend po kami.”</i> - Regent of Tau Gamma</p> <p><i>“Pero Brigada Eskwela meron pong Kick-Off.”</i>- Former SSG President</p>

4. Other Response	Statement conflicts with the other respondents.	<i>“Wala pong documents referring to the endorsement of the project, concreting of the school ground. Walang financial report maliban sa nag-closed na ako ng account.”</i> - Alumni Treasurer
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The opening or kick-off program marks the start of the implementation proper of the ASP project. Among the fourteen respondents, six confirmed that kick-off ceremony was held, and they even attended it.

The representative of Tau Gamma confidently stated, *“May kick-off ang Brigada Eskwela. Uma-attend po kami.”*

This is like the reply of the INC Deacon, *“May kick-off program ang Brigada Eskwela. Nakaka-attend po kami.”*

A concise program typically involves the attendance of Buenavista National High School (BNHS) teaching staff, project proponents, beneficiaries, and stakeholders. The project's scope of work, budget, and timeline are identified at this stage, marking the beginning of project implementation.

DepEd Order No. 66 series of 2003, included in the DepEd ASP Program Toolkit, mandates the signing of a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) prior to the implementation of larger projects. The MOA establishes collaboration arrangements, such as service partnerships or agreements for technical support and training, as outlined in Republic Act No. 8525, known as the "Adopt-a-School Act of 1998." This legislation emphasizes that a MOA should be executed between the adopting entity and the school's head, subject to assessment and approval by the Schools Division Superintendent.

Four respondents confirmed the absence of an MOA in the concreting project of the school grounds. One respondent noted the absence of documentation endorsing their project, while another attributed it to the pandemic, indicating challenges in implementation despite consistent observation of Kick-Off Ceremonies.

To ensure alignment with departmental guidelines outlined in R.A. 8525, documents were scrutinized and analysed at each project implementation level.

Table 9 presents the varied forms of documents per implementation level of the Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National High School.

Table 9

Buenavista National High School Adopt-a-School Programs and Brigada Eskwela Documents Used in Every Phase of the Implementation

ASP	Pre-implementation						Implementation			Post-implementation		
	Root Cause Analysis	Resource Gap Analysis	Project Proposal	DOD & DOA	Resource Mobilization	MOA	Daily Accomplishment Report	Attendance of Volunteers/Beneficiaries	Monitoring Form	Evaluation Form	Endorsement Papers	Financial Report
Brigada Eskwela	/	/	Not Required	/	/	Not Required	/	/	/	/	/	/

Concreting of School Ground	/	/	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
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ASP	Pre-implementation						Implementation			Post-implementation		
	Root Cause Analysis	Resource Gap Analysis	Project Proposal	DOD & DOA	Resource Mobilization	MOA	Daily Accomplishment Report	Attendance of Volunteers / Beneficiaries	Monitoring Form	Evaluation Form	Endorsement Papers	Financial Report
Send off Program for Players	/	/	/	Not Required	/	Not Required	Not Required	/	/	/	Not Required	/
Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage	/	/	/	/	Not Required	Not Required	/	/	/	/	Not Required	/
HAFFMHE	/	/	/	/	Not Required	Not Required	/	/	/	/	Not Required	/

Source: BNHS' Principal's Office, BE School Coordinator, ASP School Coordinator, Guidances Offices, SSG Office

Establishing a foundation for quality, traceability, and historical recordkeeping is crucial in documenting individual documents as well as the overall documentation of projects (Verma, 2024). Table 9, detailing Buenavista National High School's Adopt-a-School Programs and associated documents for each implementation phase, highlights the specific documents required and observed during project implementation.

Most Adopt-a-School Programs (ASPs) at BNHS fall under short-term projects that do not necessitate the implementation of Memorandum of Agreements (MOAs). Because of this, during the pre-implementation phase, common required forms include Root Cause Analysis, Resource Gap Analysis, Project Proposal, Deed of Donation, Deed of Acceptance, and for Brigada Eskwela (BE), a Resource Mobilization Form.

Archiving school project documents means they are available for anybody to refer to when working on similar projects or other related programs and projects. When a program or a project is completed, proper documentation and accomplishment reports and documentation must be filed and data in your school records management system be readily available anytime (Moensted, 2023).

If the project involves a school and its learners and it is a public school, everyone has the right to access every whereabouts that involves the school and its learners. This means the public has the right to its documentation, this is school-based management system.

Each ASP at BNHS underwent root cause analysis and resource gap analysis, as stated by the respondents in Table 9. Some documents were not applicable or required for certain ASPs, such as the absence of a project proposal for BE due to its annual nature and distinct implementation guidelines. Conversely, the Concreting of the School Grounds project primarily utilized Root Cause Analysis and Resource Gap Analysis, with other forms being less evident in its pre-implementation phase, as noted by respondents and observed during document scrutiny.

The former TIC mentioned during the interview:

“Wala pong MOA. Hindi ako aware na may MOA before. May financial report na pinasa for reporting sa school as a form of a donation from the Alumni”

She hesitated to demand the document since the Alumni Association initiated to accomplish the said project.

For other ASPs of the school, the School ASP Coordinator confirmed the needless of securing the MOA since most of the provisions were consumables and in short term.

“Wala pong MOA ang Send-off Program for Players and Teenage Pregnancy dahil mga short term ASPs ito.”, stated by the ASP Coordinator.

In compliance with Section D Statement of Goals, Policies, and Principles of the Guidelines for Building Partnerships for the K–12 Basic Education Program outlined in DepEd Order No. 40 Series of 2015, all school-level partnerships are mandated to be governed by a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA), while partnerships at the division, regional, and national levels should, at a minimum, be covered by a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU). It is imperative that all cooperative endeavors adhere to prevailing laws and DepEd directives, especially those concerning child protection.

This statements clearly cited the needs of proper documentation in relation to conducting school-related programs that requires partnership or involvement of sponsoring agency or organizations, specially Adopt-a-School Program that involves great value of assistance. This is also embedded in the guidelines of conducting the ASP.

Table 10 presents the documents utilized by Buenavista National High School to verify the transfer of donations to the school.

Table 10

Implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School-Program in Terms of the Documents to Confirm Transfer of Donations

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Documented	ASPs of BNHS were mostly well documented or followed the procedure of the department in accepting donations as stated in the ASP Guidelines	<p><i>“Deed of donation, acceptance. No MOA. No MOU or Memorandum of Understanding. Office to Office.” - the present principal</i></p> <p><i>“Deed of donations for consumables. Deed of acceptance for non-consumable, long term. Madalas ay pahatid lang ang items pero noted and reported.” - ASP Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Property Custodian at ASP ay may napapirmahan na Deed of Donation. Ang mga through G-cash o transmittal ay may confirmation sa messenger. Pinapadalan din po sila ng DOD na pinipirmahan ng representative nila.” - BE Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Usually po ay attendance, types of service rendered.” - Tau Gamma Regent</i></p>

"Meron pong documents na napirmahan sa school, attendance. Kumpleto." - INC Deacon

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
2. Undocumented	Other officers of the governing bodies were not informed about the endorsement document in another project.	<p><i>"Ang napansin ko po sa concreting ay walang documents akong nakikita as SSG President. Baka po sa principal meron.</i></p> <p><i>Ang papel ko po as SSG nun ay magsa-ayos nung mga students."</i>, the former SSG President</p> <p><i>"Walang documents." - Former TIC</i></p> <p><i>"Wala pong document refers to the endorsement of the project. Walang financial report maliban sa klinosed ko na ang account namin dito sa province. Binayaran lahat. Kasama ko si _____ sa pag closed sa account." - Alumni Treasurer</i></p>
3. Unaware Officer	The officer was not aware about the endorsement document	<i>"Hindi ko alam kung meron" - Former PTA President</i>

The data in Table 10 provides a summary of the documents utilized during implementation, including those that were successfully accomplished and those that were not. This summary is based on the statements of respondents. Five out of the nine respondents confirmed witnessing the implementation of project documentation and even signed the necessary forms.

For short-term assistance, a Deed of Donation (DOD) is typically completed by the donor.

"Property Custodian at ASP ay may napapirmahan na deed of donation.", stated by the BE Coordinator.

During the interview, the principal commented, *"Deed of donation, acceptance. No MOA. No MOU or Memorandum of Understanding. Office to Office"*.

These were all the usual documents being accomplished during ASPs in BNHS. In most ASPs of BNHS, DOD was being accomplished by the donors to be forwarded to the resource mobilization group in BE. In contrast, in other ASPs, the form may be directly given to the BNHS's ASP Coordinator and are subject to consolidation for updating the BNHS' ASP database.

According to the deacon volunteer, *"Meron pong documents na napirmahan na forms sa school, attendance. Kumpleto."*

The volunteers' attendance sheets for BE, ASP, and HAFFMHE were signed after they received their supplies.

But three of the respondents expressed the opposite reaction. According to them, there were no documents observed during the endorsement of one of the projects, the concreting of school grounds, nor getting the attendance of the *workers*.

“Ang napansin ko po sa concreting ay walang documents akong nakikita.” commented by the former SSG President, when he was asked about the project’s documentation.

Furthermore, this was confirmed by the statement of the former TIC,
“Walang documents.”

According to the Alumni Treasurer, the laborers in the latter part of the project were being compensated by the Alumni Association.

Most of the ASPs of BNHS were short-term and thus did not require MOA. The common forms needed during the implementation were the resource gap analysis tool, project proposal, deed of donation, deed of acceptance, financial report, and attendance sheet.

Although BE is an ASP, this does not require each school to make a project proposal because it is DepEd’s flagship ASP project. Other projects, like the Forum on Teenage Pregnancy, are coordinated annually with the LGU and the Population Commission (POPCOM), and a MOA has not yet been executed but rather between The Buenavista Teen Center (BTC) and POPCOM.

The documents that were utilized during the implementation and the documents that failed to be accomplished were summarized in Table 9, Buenavista National High School Adopt-a-School Programs and Brigada Eskwela Documents Used in Every Phase of the Implementation. This was confirmed by the statements of the respondents in Table 10, Implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School-Program in Terms of the Documents to Confirm Transfer of Donations. Among the nine respondents (9) who answered the question referring to documentation of ASP, five (5) of them confirmed that they witnessed the implementation of documenting the projects and they even signed in the forms.

For short-term assistance, a DOD is accomplished by the donor.

“Property Custodian at ASP ay may napapirmahan na deed of donation.”, stated by the BE Coordinator.

During the interview, the principal commented, "Deed of donation, acceptance. No MOA. No MOU or Memorandum of Understanding. Office to Office". These were all the usual documents being accomplished during ASPs in BNHS.

In most ASPs of BNHS, DOD was being accomplished by the donors to be forwarded to the resource mobilization group in BE. In contrast, in other ASPs, the form may be directly given to the BNHS’s ASP Coordinator and are subject to consolidation for updating the BNHS’ ASP database.

According to the deacon volunteer,
“Meron pong documents na napirmahan na forms sa school, attendance. Kumpleto.”

The volunteers' attendance sheets for BE, ASP, and HAFFMHE were signed after they received their supplies.

But three (3) of the respondents expressed opposite reaction. According to them, there were no documents observed during the endorsement of one of the projects, the concreting of school grounds, neither getting the attendance of the workers.

“Ang napansin ko po sa concreting ay walang documents akong nakikita.” commented by the former SSG President, when he was asked about the project’s documentation. Furthermore, this was confirmed by the statement of the former TIC *“Walang documents.”*

According to the Alumni Treasurer, the laborers in the latter part of the project were being compensated by the Alumni Association.

Most of the ASPs of BNHS were short-term and thus do not require MOA. The common forms needed during the implementation were the resource gap analysis tool, project proposal, deed of donation, deed of acceptance, financial report, and attendance sheet.

Although BE is an ASP, this does not require each school to make a project proposal because it is DepEd’s flagship ASP project. Other projects, like the Forum on Teenage Pregnancy, are coordinated annually with the LGU and the Population Commission (POPCOM), and a MOA has not yet been executed but rather between The Buenavista Teen Center (BTC) and POPCOM.

At present, the Rural Health Office of the LGU of Buenavista, under the leadership of the detailed public physician, is taking the initiative of conducting the forum in the different secondary schools of the district in partnership with the POPCOM. The sense of needing to conduct the program in every school was anticipated due to the progressive cases of teenage pregnancies and early marriage, making the municipality the second in rank among the six municipalities in the entire province as revealed by the RHU. In the previous conduct of the project, it was the LGU that requested the presence of the school’s target population.

Implementation Proper Phase

This phase denotes the process of putting a project into action to produce the deliverables. Project coordinators, proponents, and ASP members managed resources and measured performances under the guidance of the BNHS’ principal to ensure that the project stayed within its planned scope and budget.

The work of the project is carried out, and the adopt-a-school project plan is put into action during the implementation. It is critical to keep everything under control and communicate as needed when implementing. Continuous progress monitoring allows for necessary adjustments to be made, which are then documented as deviations from the original plan. This is the step where a project manager, usually the head of the school, spends most of his time.

During the implementation phase of an ASP the following documents must be evident as stated in the guidelines: Daily Accomplishment Report, Attendance Sheet of Volunteers or Beneficiaries and Monitoring Form. These forms were mostly accomplished during the implementation of the Brigada Eskwela as shown by the documents presented during the

data gathering phase of this study. This was supported by the statements of the respondents during the face-to-face interview being reflected in the next section of this paper.

Table 11 containing the statements of the respondents during the face-to-face interview about the sufficiency of the supplies for the different Adopt-A-School Programs.

Table 11

Implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School-Program in Terms of Sufficiency of Supplies for the Implementation of the Project

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Sufficiency of Outsourced Supplies for the	Sufficiency of materials; outsourced and from MOOE depending on the number of volunteers	“Kalimitan ay sobra. Pag may excess ay inatabi muna. Maga-isip muna ng isang proyekto o baka may isang guro na nangangailangan at may project sila sa room ay duon abigay.” - present principal
implementation of the project	and the scope of work they can cover during their scheduled period	<p>“Sapat ang materials dahil natapos ang project through alumni.” - the former TIC.</p> <p>“Sapat naman ang naging amount incurred. May nai-forward pa na natirang budget sa susunod na PTA Officers.” - Former PTA</p> <p>“Sapat naman ang pondo. Natapos ang project.” - Alumni Treasurer</p> <p>“Sapat ang gamit para sa labor na nakalaan. Mabilis matapos ang gawain.” - INC Deacon</p> <p>“Sapat naman po sa palagay ko. Nung tapos na po yung pag concrete ng ground ay may mga tira pa pong sacks of cement. Hindi ko lang po alam kung saan nagamit yung sobra. Hindi po kami na-inform as SSG.” - Former SSG President</p>
2. Insufficiency of DepEd Supplies	Lacking in some materials provided by the MOOE that were being outsourced	<p>“Usually ay kulang ang materials for repairs. Dahil sa repairs ay maraming kailangan. Katulad po nyan ay repairs or replacement ng jealousies, doorknobs, and electric supplies. Kalimitan ay to follow na lang yung iba. Bukod sa services ay may materials din silang dala.” - BE Coordinator</p> <p>“Kulang po kadalasan ang supplies from DepEd kaya ina-outsource. Kapag kulang pa rin po ang na-outsourced, teachers ang nagadagdag. Ipapasok na donation na yun nung teacher reported as donation ng teacher.” - ASP Coordinator</p>
3. Refreshments Never Fails	Foods for the volunteer were assured every time	“Hindi ko po naman masasabi na sobra. Hindi ko rin po masabina kulang. Pay minsan po ay depende sa pagkakataon. Minsan po ay may kinakailangang gamit. Minsan ay kulang. Ang hindi po nawawala dyan tuwing naga volunteer kami ay, ang maganda po dyan ay lagi silang may pa-meryenda sa amin. So naa-appreciate namin yun, dahil parang yun lang ang ganansya namin sa aming serbisyo.” Tau Gamma Regent

The ability of the school will be tested during the implementation of a program, especially when most of the supplies will be outsourced. Reyes (2023) stated that the renowned management expert Peter Drucker famously advised to do the best and outsource the rest. A school truly needs the cooperation of the entire village to achieve success in every endeavor.

About 88% of the respondents' population confirmed the sufficiency of the supplies when conducting an ASP program.

With the positive response of the community, resources for the various ASPs of BNHS were commonly sufficient, as stated by the present principal.

"Kalimitan ay sobra. Pag may excess ay inatabi muna. Maga-isip muna ng isang proyekto o baka may isang guro na nangangailangan at may project sila sa room ay duon abigay."

This was supported by the statement of the INC Deacon,
"Sapat ang gamit para sa labor na nakalaan. Mabilis matapos ang gawain."

The statement of the SSG President on the concreting of the school grounds was parallel to the statements of the other respondents,

"Sapat naman po sa palagay ko. Nung tapos na po yung pag concrete ng ground ay may mga tira pa pong sacks of cement."

On the other hand, supplies from DepEd were commonly not enough, as commented by the ASP Coordinator,

"Kulang po kadalasan ang supplies from DepEd kaya ina-outsource."

In the ASPs stated herein, sufficiency of the materials was achieved with the assistance of the donors.

The sufficiency and insufficiency depend on the circumstance, as stated by one group of volunteers,

"... minsan po ay depende sa pagkakataon..., ang maganda po dyan ay lagi silang may pa-meryenda sa amin. So naa-appreciate namin yun, dahil parang yun lang ang ganansya namin sa aming serbisyo."

There were circumstances when volunteers provide for the lacking materials just to maximize the time they would render. Sometimes the teachers provided the lacking materials just to ensure completion of the work.

"Kapag kulang pa rin po ang na-outsourced, teachers ang nagadagdag. Ipapasok na donation na yun ng teacher, reported as donation ng teacher."

This denotes that the volunteer themselves found ways to remedy the problems that came along the ways of implementing the ASP.

Table 12 presents the problems encountered and remedied during the implementation phase of the ASPs.

Table 12

Implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School-Program in Terms of the Problems Encountered During the Implementation

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Problems Encountered	<p>Hindrance in any form that meddled during the implementation of the projects</p> <p>Nature-related problems that hinder the implementation of the ASP</p>	<p><i>“Natural or nature-related problems commonly like naga-ulan, mainit, etc. Paghanap ng skilled workers fit the job.”</i> - the present principal.</p> <p><i>“Yung weather. Laging naga-ulan nung inagawa ‘yung grounds.”</i> - the Alumni Treasurer</p> <p><i>“Documentations ang common problems kapag may projects. Ang nangyayari ay isa o dalawang tao lang ang gumagawa ng report although may mga tao dun sa iba’t-ibang tao ang naka-assign. Hindi pa rin na-address. A-inform dapat ang designated person about the functions and roles. Kung ano ang function mo dun ka lang.”</i> - the ASP Coordinator</p> <p><i>“Security ng mga bata at safety ng mga bata. Always remind the learners to be safe. Nag-meeting ang faculty.”</i> - Former TIC</p> <p><i>“Ang common problems po ay materials. Marami po ang labor supplies. Namo-monitor ang percentage ng work done sa daily accomplishment report. Usually, po ay sa materyales ang problema. Wala nang magamit na materyales ang volunteer sa labor.”</i> - BE Coordinator</p> <p><i>“Kalimitan kulang ang gamit sobra ang skilled workers. Inasabi po sa guro ang kulang at inabili ang kulang na gamit.”</i> - INC Deacon</p> <p><i>“Nung naga-implement po ay on-going ang mga klase, tapos ang problema po ay hindi makapag-flag ceremony sa ground. Sa tapat or pasilyo ng room ang formation ng mga students during flag ceremony. Ang isa pa pong problema ay pag napasok ang mga estudyante ay medyo siksikan ang mga daan, crowded ang hallways. Kinausap po kami ni Ma’am Laarni para makatulong sa traffic ng mga bata ‘tas one pathway lang gagamitin.”</i> - Former SSG President</p> <p><i>“Ang normaling nai-encounter namin halimbawa sa internal problem kasi dito na ‘yung mga residente, mga brod coming from Bagacay ay yung transportation allowance. Minsan ay ina-shoulder po ng aming pondo.”</i> - Tau Gamma Regent</p>
2. No Problem Encountered	<p>There was awareness of the stakeholders regarding the project</p>	<p><i>“Wala namang problems encountered dahil alam naman ng lahat na kaylangan yan.”</i> - Former PTA President</p>

In any project, program, or endeavour, risk equals success. A good school leader or project manager can achieve this by employing the appropriate strategy. Furthermore, school administrators demonstrate effective leadership by delegating authority to others and engage in collaborative, cooperative, participative, democratic, and focused leadership styles (Senjaya, 2019).

Among the common hindrances encountered during the ASP implementation of BNHS were natural risks that are out of human control, the unending needs for materials once the work started, and the very challenging documentation for every phase of the program.

“Natural or nature-related problems commonly like naga-ulan, mainit, etc. Paghanap ng skilled workers fit for the job.”

This was seconded by the Alumni Treasurer stating,
“Yung weather. Laging naga-ulan nung inagawa ‘yung ground.”

A few identified differentiated challenges occurred while implementing the cited ASPs of BNHS.

Among these were:

“Ang common problems po ay materials. Marami po ang labor supplies.”, according to the School BE Coordinator.

This was supported by the statement,

“Kalimitan kulang ang gamit, sobra ang skilled workers. Inasabi po sa guro ang kulang at inabili ang kulang na gamit.”, commented by the one of the leaders of volunteers on problems occurred and the safety of the students.

Another form of challenge is the security of the learners during the concreting of the school grounds as stated by the former TIC of the school.

“Security ng mga bata at safety ng mga bata. Always remind the learners to be safe. Nag-meeting ang faculty.”

On the part of the brotherhood member volunteers, the common problem was the budget for fare of the group,

“Ang normaling nai-encounter namin halimbawa sa internal problem kasi dito na ‘yung mga residente, mga brod coming from Bagacay ay yung transportation allowance. Minsan ay ina-shoulder po ng aming pondo.”

For the ASP Coordinator of BNHS, the challenge that must be given thorough attention is the proper documentation of every ASP.

“Documentations ang common problems kapag may projects. Ang nangyayari ay isa o dalawang tao lang ang gumagawa ng report although may mga tao dun sa iba’t-ibang tao ang naka-assign. Hindi pa rin na-aaddress. A-inform dapat ang designated person about the functions and roles. Kung ano ang function mo dun ka lang.”

To guarantee that all parties involved are aware of the goals, deliverables, schedule, progress, and other aspects of the project, documentation is crucial. Inadequate paperwork can make it simple for misunderstandings and miscommunications to happen, which can cause delays or even project failure (Moensted, 2023).

Somehow, on the part of the former PTA President, the awareness of everyone about the project prohibited any problem.

“Wala namang problems encountered dahil alam naman ng lahat na kaylangan yan.”

This was supported by Barret (2023) who stated that goals that are specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) help to ensure that stakeholders are “on the same page” about the planned work.

A thorough planned program will surely achieve its set goal and minimizes its conflict. BNHS proved that all are subject to adjustment and adherence to the set objectives regardless of the ASP will truly yield a positive outcome.

No one is perfect, not even highly trained school managers, but for a school, each component has a responsibility to use all their capabilities to ensure that the project does not fail. After all, the school is counting on this to work. When proposing a project to prospective sponsors, the proponent is essentially promising to execute it successfully, and failure to do so for any reason will affect the credibility of the person, group, or organization. Careful planning and strong leadership can go a long way in ensuring the success of an adopt-a-school project.

Table 13 summarizes the various hindrances or common problems encountered, interventions made and the stakeholders who took the appropriate actions in pursuing the different Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National High School.

Table 13

Adopt-a-School-Programs of Buenavista National High School: Common Problems Encountered, Interventions and Stakeholders Who Made the Intervention

ASP	Common Problems Encountered During Implementation	Intervention	Stakeholder Who Made the Intervention
Brigada Eskwela	Insufficiency of materials for the repair and repaint	Donation of necessary materials	Volunteers, Donors, SSG & PTA
	Over supply of skilled workers to render their services during the day	Rescheduling of the labor service provider	PTA, Volunteer Organizations Volunteers & Organizations
	Transportation of group of volunteers from other towns Documentations of the outsourced materials (personal tapping and direct endorsement of the materials to the teacher-adviser)	Provision from the groups' fund Centralized documentation and endorsement of the donations	ASP Coordinator and BE Committee Members

ASP	Common Problems Encountered During Implementation	Intervention	Stakeholder Who Made the Intervention
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Send off Program 2023	Additional members of the delegation (beneficiaries) who were not included in the memorandum	Consummation of the buffer pack of goods	Donors and Sponsors
Forum Teenage Pregnancy & Early Marriage 2019	Behavior of the students during the forum	Speakers strategic approach in getting the attention of the attendees	Partner Agencies - RHU and PNP
HAFFMHE	Cancellation of the delivery of goods from donors outside the province due to bad weather	Outsourcing the necessary supplies for the completion of the project	Organizers of the ASP
Concreting of School Grounds	Resource constraint to cover the concreting of the entire grounds Nature-related e.g. heavy rain, insufficiency of materials	Outsourcing the necessary supplies for the completion of the project Rescheduling of the scheduled work	Alumni, PTA and SSG PTA Officers, Alumni and Project Coordinators

Source: BNHS ASP School Coordinator, BNHS BE School Coordinator, Guidance Designates, PTA Officers, Groups of Volunteers

Barret (2023) emphasized the significance of planning in the proverb "if you fail to plan, plan to fail," particularly applicable to launching new projects in schools. A well-defined plan and a dedicated implementation team are crucial for project progression. The proactive approach of BNHS school administrators in planning and executing projects significantly contributed to achieving set goals, notwithstanding challenges encountered in their Adopt-a-School Programs (ASPs).

Table 13, "ASPs of Buenavista National High School: Common Problems Encountered, Intervention and Stakeholders Who Made the Intervention," illustrates the various issues encountered during BNHS ASP implementations, alongside interventions and involved stakeholders ensuring project success. Stakeholder involvement, including PNP, RHU, PTA, SSG, Alumni, Volunteers, and other organizations, played a pivotal role in refining and completing projects.

Despite anticipated difficulties, maintaining positivity towards goal attainment is imperative, necessitating teamwork and unity to overcome obstacles. Alomes (2020) advocates for meaningful interaction and collaboration among all education stakeholders to foster effective learning environments and systems. Every facet of the learning environment must contribute to achieving success in educational endeavors, as observed in BNHS ASP implementations.

During Brigada Eskwela (BE) implementation, common challenges included material shortages and transportation costs for organization members, often covered by the volunteering group funds. Weather-related factors also impacted activities such as school ground concreting.

Table 14 below elucidates the respondents' statements related to the monitoring of Buenavista National High School's Adopt-a-School Programs.

Table 14

Implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School Programs in Terms of Monitoring of the Project

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Project Monitoring	Refers to updated progress of the project's implementation	<p><i>"Pagdating sa monitoring aside sa may assign ka bilang head ay ginagawa mo talaga ang monitoring and implementation para ma-monitor ang progress at quality. Ako mismo ang napili. Halimbawa ay sa kulay. Nasabi ko "Gusto ko'y ganyan." Inabigay at ina-check ko ang design. Inapabago ko, inapalitanpag hindi ko nagugustuhan o palagay ko hindi matibay. Sa BE may daily monitoring progress." - the present principal</i></p> <p><i>"Monthly Report and Partnership Database. Monthly posting of donations." - ASP Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>"Every day tsine-check ang report gamit ang daily accomplishment report form." - BE Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>"Pinupuntahan naman natin. Bawat year level ay may assigned day at mino-monitor naman kung may ginagawa talaga. May attendance naman ang mga vlunteers. Hinahabol para sa graduation yung concreting 'nung school ground." - Former PTA President.</i></p> <p><i>"Usually naman din po ay nata-track din naman namin yung progress. So, halimbawa, kasi po ay ina-recognized din po 'yung effort. Halimbawa'y nakatanggap ng certificate, meaning ay naging successful po ang mga projects." - Tau Gamma Regent</i></p> <p><i>"Attendance at may monitoring ng trabaho. May mga teachers na natingin sa trabaho ng volunteer." - INC Deacon</i></p>
2. No monitoring	Other personalities failed to monitor the project	<p><i>"Wala po. Umalis na rin si Sir President. Nag-online na lang siguro sila sa evaluation and endorsement." - Alumni Treasurer</i></p> <p><i>"Sa side po ng SSG ay wala kaming document na hawak about tracking of the project. Maybe sa side po ng gumawa o sa principal." - Former SSG President</i></p> <p><i>"May plan naman shinare through verbal, walang document. Nakahiyang mag demand dahil wala tayong share sa project." - Former TIC</i></p>

Monitoring is the ongoing evaluation of a project or program in respect to the predetermined timeline for implementation. It is also a useful management tool that, when utilized correctly, ought to offer ongoing input on how the project is being carried out and help identify potential obstacles and triumphs so that choices can be made quickly (Otieno, 2019).

Most of the ASPs were monitored by the implementing authorities and there were circumstances when monitoring was not required and observed as revealed by the statements of the respondents.

The school principal and other implementing officers monitored the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP). Progress report forms were being accomplished and submitted as reflected in Table 9, Buenavista National High School Adopt-a-School Program and Brigada Eskwela Documents Used During the Entire Implementation.

“Pagdating sa monitoring, aside sa may assigned ka bilang head ay ginagawa mo talaga ang monitoring and implementation para ma-monitor ang progress at quality.”

As for the ASP,

“May Monthly Report and Partnership Database. Monthly posting of donations.”

The BE Coordinator supported the statement,

“Every day tsine-check ang report gamit ang Daily Accomplishment Report Form ng Brigada Eskwela.”

Even the former PTA President has the same stance on this,

“Pinupuntahan naman natin. Bawat year level ay may assigned day at mino-monitor naman kung may ginagawa talaga. May attendance naman ang mga volunteers.”

Appendix S, "Brigada Eskwela Form 06 Daily Accomplishment Report Form," and Appendix Q, "Brigada Eskwela Form 04 Daily Attendance of Volunteers Monitoring Form," were utilized to track project progress, aligning with implementing guidelines for Brigada Eskwela (BE). Per BE guidelines, all relevant forms were submitted to the division office for evaluation once a school was nominated for Best Brigada Implementer.

Contrastingly, no specific document within the Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) toolkit was designated for project monitoring. The ASP Toolkit outlines fourteen sections for implementation, with related documents including the MOA (Appendix L), DOD (Appendix J), DOA (Appendix K), and Resource Gap Analysis (Appendix I). In the absence of a dedicated ASP Monitoring Form, monitoring efforts relied on observation, with each implementing body office contributing to the process.

SSG and alumni members occasionally faced limitations in accessing project monitoring yet remained vigilant in coordinating for student safety and welfare.

“Sa side po ng SSG ay wala kaming document na hawak about the tracking of the project.”, recalled by the former SSG President.

For the treasurer of the alumni, she was unaware if there was communication about the status of the project.

“Wala po. Umalis na rin si Sir President. Nag-online na lang siguro sila sa evaluation and endorsement.”

The former school TIC's statement somehow supported the alumni treasurer's statement, *“May plan naman shinare through verbal, walang document. Nakahiyang mag demand dahil wala tayong share sa project.”*

A project's ability to succeed depends on thorough and ongoing project monitoring.

With careful project monitoring, a school head can obtain important information about how a project is progressing and utilize that information to make well-informed decisions.

Table 15 presents the Management and Evaluation Framework of the Department of Education and the responsibilities of each implementing offices to ensure the success implementation of any program of the government in relation to education.

Table 15

Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework Section VIII Roles and Responsibilities of Offices

National	Secretary	Planning Service	All operating units
Regional	Regional Director	Quality Assurance Division	All operating units
School Division	Schools Division Superintendent	School Governance and Operations Division	All operating units
School	School Head	School Head	All personnel and stakeholders in the school

Note: Reprinted from "DepEd Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (BEMEF)," by M.A. Llego. Copyright 2024 by "TeachePh."

Table 15, entitled "Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework Section VIII Roles and Responsibilities of Offices," delineates the Measurement and Evaluation (M&E) System and the corresponding lead, process owner, and responsible offices within the Department of Education's (DepEd) Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (BEMEF). Aligned with Republic Acts (RA) 9155, the "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001," and RA 10533, the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013," DepEd undertakes significant projects, programs, and activities to ensure accessibility and quality improvement in basic education, with all operational units at governance levels accountable for achieving this objective. Table 15 illustrates how measurement and evaluation will be conducted across educational offices, with corresponding lead roles, process owners, and responsible offices. BEMEF is intricately linked to the planning and budgetary strategy of the Department.

At the school level, the school head assumes immediate responsibility for project monitoring and evaluation, as indicated in the table. Various measures were implemented to ensure projects were monitored and completed according to departmental protocols. Despite some individuals lacking direct access to project monitoring, they observed project progress, with representatives from their bodies attending monitoring sessions. The absence of a monitoring form for regular ASPs did not impede the school's ability to track progress, as implementing officers were present throughout the process. Otieno (2019) advised implementing officers and project managers to collaborate on establishing suitable monitoring and assessment systems.

Continuous and thorough project monitoring is vital for project success. Florida Tech (2018) emphasized that school heads can gather crucial insights into project progress through meticulous monitoring, enabling informed decision-making. BNHS's holistic involvement in its ASPs significantly contributed to achieving set goals.

The set goals will not be achieved without assuring that a project is proceeding according to schedule and that its tasks are being performed through project monitoring. In this, numerous indicators need to be tracked, including the budget, the completion time, and the quality standard. The significance of each varies based on the project's nature. Anticipating future needs is another aspect of project monitoring.

The subsequent table, Table 16, summarizes notable beneficiary experiences regarding ASP implementation which discovered after monitoring the ASPs.

Table 16

Implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School-Program in Terms of Experiences of the Beneficiaries

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Self-fulfilling Theme	The pleasant feeling experienced by the various components of the ASP of BNHS	<p>“Sa Pre andun ang mga negative thoughts ang mga na-tap. Sino ‘yung mga taong masuporta sa iyo? Identification ng stakeholders, technical working group ay kailangan. Post-implementation, documentation and consolidation difficulty. Kailangan tapos na, may gawain pa pala kaso alumni na ang nag-accomplish. Sa implementation may mga pagkakataon na kulang ang mga gamit at pagbabas. na tulong ng tao. Kusa na silang pumupunta during implementation kung and manang inatulong nila. Every year yun kailan na buman sa manrag na taon. Nag-o-offer pa sila basta Brigada Eskwela na dahil na-aannounce naman sa national tv.” - BE Coordinator</p> <p>“Pre. Thinking na imposible masolusyunan ang pag-concrete ng ground. Grabbed the opportunity when they offered the project implementation. Meron nga kaming malaking amount, kaya maibigay ang pangangailangan ng school. Maraming plano pa sa sensibility. Alumni treasure.”</p> <p>“Nung pre-implementation, malaking honor ‘yung pinoposed ko. Nakaka-proud na sinuportahan ng LGU ang project natin. Overwhelming. Nung during, na-dis appoint po kami kasi may proposal po kaming sinubmit para sa paggawa kaso wala kaming nagawa. Okay lang din kasi there’s nothing we can do rin dahil students kami. The least that we did was pag-facilitate ng mga students para di magka-problema sa paggawa. Okay naman po it was a big help for the students and the teachers.” - the Former SSG President</p> <p>“Masaya. Nakaka-inspire ang mga ginagawa nila. Masasaya ang mga guro. Nagagawa ang mga dapat gawin.” (Masaya at nakangiti na naghahayag). - INC Deacon</p> <p>“Ano po sya ay, ahm, magandang experience kasi nakakatulong ka eh. Ang pagtulong po ay malaking bagay. Kumbaga, tumulong ka sa school, pero eventually hindi naman ‘yung school ang natulungan mo kundi yung mga bata nanag-aaral dun so magiging multiplier effect ‘yung iyong tulong.</p>

			<p><i>So, accomplishing po sya, isang magandang bagay na ginawa mo sa iyon kapwa at sa community na kinabibilangan mo.</i></p> <p><i>“Sa post-implementation ay self-fulfilling kasi nakapagbigay ka ng serbisyo na walang kapalit. (Nakangiti na may pag-aalinlangan) - Tau Gamma Regent</i></p>
2. Challenging	There was problem encountered but was managed	was	<p><i>“Mahirap mag-implement ng project lalong-lalo na kung di-gusto ng nakararami. ‘Yung 50 pesos ay ang hirap singilin. Ayaw din ni Sir Matibag magpasingil. Medyo challenging. Voluntary. Kesa mag-solicit ay nag-fund raising tayo. Para naman sa school yan, sa bata at sa nakararami.” - Former PTA President</i></p> <p><i>“Post implementation ang pinakamahirap. ‘Pag di properly documented. Minsan ay through GC.” - the ASP Coordinator</i></p>

During the implementation phase of Adopt-a-School Programs (ASPs), beneficiaries' and respondents' experiences were classified into two categories: self-fulfilling and challenging, reflecting on their responses.

For implementing bodies, the most rewarding aspect post-ASPs was fulfilment, as indicated by their responses. Aranda et al. (2019) identified key indicators of self-fulfilment, including values, knowledge, self-esteem enhancement, social factors, and particularly the accomplishment of tasks.

Apprehensions were prevalent during each implementation phase, particularly among implementing bodies. From the initial step of problem identification, ideas to address the issues seemed boundless.

During the pre-implementation phase, primary concerns revolved around obtaining body approval for the idea, feasibility of project implementation, strategies for fundraising, and identification of potential partners.

“Sa pre andun ang mga apprehensions. Ang hirap sa planning. Mahirap mag-tap ng tao. May mga negative thoughts ang ibang mga na-tap...”, smilingly uttered by the present principal.

For the former TIC, on concreting of the school ground.

“Pre. Thinking na imposible masolusyunan ang pag-concrete ng ground. I grabbed the opportunity when they offered the project.”

The former TIC expressed that the pre-implementation phase was the most challenging aspect of ASP implementation for her. This sentiment aligns with the findings of Barret et al. (2023), who suggested that individuals exhibiting a strong commitment to a course of action, even in the face of adverse outcomes, may be experiencing escalation of commitment.

For the former SSG President, as a student,

“Nung pre-implementation, malaking honor ‘yung prinoposed ko. Nakaka-proud na sinuportahan ng LGU ang project natin. Overwhelming.”

During the implementation period, the following concerns surfaced; sufficiency of the funds to cover the entire project, possible alternative source of fund in case of insufficiency, and the possibility of utilizing the MOOE in case of insufficiency.

“...may mga pagkakataon na kulang ang mga gamit at panahon.”, answered by the present principal.

The same worry was felt by the former PTA President,
“Mahirap mag-implement ng project lalong-lalo na kung di-gusto ng nakararami. ‘Yung 50 pesos ay ang hirap singilin. Ayaw din ni Sir Matibag magpasingil. Medyo challenging. Voluntary...”

For the school BE Coordinator, there was a sense of assurance that the project would be completed due to the regular cooperation of the stakeholders.

“Buhos na tulong ng tao. Kusa na silang pumupunta during implementation kung ano man ang maitulong nila. Every year yun kahit na dumaaan sa mahirap na taon. Maraming regular na nagbibigay at regular na tumutulong. Nag-o-offer na sila...”

For a group of volunteers like the Tau Gamma, helping the school means assisting all the components of the school, especially the learners. When people recognize and appreciate their efforts, volunteers are most at ease (Muller, 2018).

“...Kumbaga, tumulong ka sa school, pero eventually hindi naman ‘yung school ang natulungan mo kundi yung mga bata na nag-aaral dun so magiging multiplier effect ‘yung iyong tulong. So, accomplishing po sya...”

On the other hand, the post-implementation phase is the less-worrying phase most of the time. It is somehow crucial when it comes to documents that would justify the credibility of the project’s implementation. The principal said:

“Sa post-implementation, reporting, and consolidation of documents ng bawat in-charge ang challenge. In post-implementation. Documentation and consolidation difficulty. Feeling tapos na, may gawain pa pala kaso alumni na ang nag-accomplished.”

The above statements of the implementing bodies proved Barret et al. (2023) claim that the psychological characteristics that affect the escalation of commitment are determinants that center on how people's cognitive and affective processes may lead them to persist in their unsuccessful path. Because of those different inevitable aspects of implementing a project, the success of the project became more persistent.

“Sa post-implementation ay self-fulfilling kasi nakapagbigay ka ng serbisyo na walang kapalit.”, the answer of the Tau Gamma Regent.

Same with the representative of the INC Volunteer Group.

“Masaya. Nakaka-inspire ang mga ginagawa nila. Masasaya ang mga guro. Nagagawa ang mga dapat gawin.”, the Deacon was smiling when answering the question.

Challenging was the immense feeling felt by the former PTA President during the implementation period. For the ASP Coordinator it was during post-implementation period.

The Former PTA President though challenged had an option of performing his duties, *“Mahirap mag-implement ng project lalong-lalo na kung di-gusto ng nakararami. ‘Yung 50 pesos ay ang hirap singilin. Ayaw din ng dating superentindent magpasingil. Medyo challenging. Voluntary. Kesa mag-solicit ay nag-fund raising tayo...”*

This is the most difficult period for an ASP School Coordinator like me, *“Post implementation ang pinakamahirap. ‘Pag di properly documented. Minsan ay through GC.”*

For volunteers, engaging in ASP implementation represents a profoundly self-fulfilling endeavor. Despite the absence of monetary compensation, Muller (2018) underscored that volunteers may seek reciprocal exchanges and equitable recognition for their efforts. Instead of financial remuneration, volunteers value non-monetary gestures from benefactors. They understand that their efforts are integral as volunteers within the school community.

Although project execution may entail complexity, most respondents reported experiencing a sense of fulfillment upon completion, knowing they contributed to the welfare of others. Engaging in community service bolsters volunteers' confidence, as they feel a natural sense of accomplishment from helping individuals and the broader community. This sense of pride and connection to their actions leads to increased self-esteem. Segal and Robinson (n.d.) noted that volunteers who feel confident in themselves are more likely to maintain a positive outlook on life and pursue their future aspirations.

Post-implementation Phase

The post-implementation phase marks the culmination of the project's scope, aligning with the plan outlined in the project proposal or Budget of Work. This phase involves consolidating project documentation across different levels, assessing implementation and functionality, and devising a maintenance plan. Otieno (2019) emphasized that the post-implementation phase is not about assigning blame but rather identifying successful aspects and areas for improvement. Lessons learned from this phase can inform future projects, including those covered by ASPs or other school-related initiatives.

This section delves into the collective experiences of project implementers, volunteers, stakeholders, beneficiaries, and other ASP components, highlighting their perspectives on participation and the value they attribute to project implementation. It evaluates whether projects were effectively monitored and evaluated for ASP completion. Additionally, the utilization of various forms throughout implementation phases is assessed to ensure compliance with ASP implementation guidelines outlined in the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of RA 8525.

Otieno (2019) stressed that post-project evaluation entails a systematic and objective analysis of project accomplishments. He emphasized the importance of reviewing project summaries and evaluations to determine if anticipated targets were met, extract lessons learned, and provide timely feedback for future endeavors. Through this process, encountered problems are addressed, and corresponding solution measures are proposed to enhance future project implementations and ensure desired outcomes are achieved according to the project plan.

The post-mortem or post-project review is also known as the post-implementation review. The Project Implementation Review is a crucial component of the overall project planning process since it provides significantly more significant insights than just determining if the project was successful. These insights are quite helpful because they can be used as lessons learnt in any future endeavors. This is carried out in the project closure phase.

Table 17 presents respondents' statements regarding the significant of their roles and how they performed during Adopt-a-School Implementation.

Table 17

Post-implementation Phase of the Adopt-a-School-Program in Terms of the Role in the Implementation

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Significant Role	Every role performed by each component of the implementing bodies, regardless of the designation and distinction	<p><i>“Ang main role ng coordinator ay ma-inform ang mga committees kung ano ang gagawin during the BE ‘tas pag na-inform na sila yun ready na for implementation. Kanya-kanya na sila. Ako lang ‘yung parang moderator. Transparency ang talagang reason bakit bumabalik-balik sila sa school. Kitang-kita ng nag-donate kung saan napupunta ang kanyang binigay.” - BE Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Accountability. Accountable ka sa lahat ng actions, situations, at undertakings at nangyayari sa project like BE.” - Present Principal</i></p> <p><i>“It is worth it for the project. Taking the risk for the students, teachers, and school.” - Former TIC</i></p> <p><i>“Ang importansya lang ng role ko ay sa report. Dun kasi ako mapapasok at Brigada Eskwela.” - ASP Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Very important din po dahil kung hindi namin na-facilitate ‘yung mga students kung saan madaan, mapunta ay malaking tulong na rin sa pag-concrete ng ground. Hindi na namroblema ‘yung mga workers sa pagsasabi sa mga student’s kung ano dapat at hindi dapat gawin. Nakapag-focus po sila sa paggawa nila.” - Former SSG President</i></p> <p><i>“Mahalaga sya sa planning at pagda-direct nung mga myembro. Halimbawa, sino kailangan, ano dadalhin. So, para maging organisado. Kasi ito’y hindi isa o talong myembre, marami.” - Tau Gamma Regent</i></p> <p><i>“Kasiyahan ng Dyos. Napupuri ang gawa ng kapatiran. Kapurihan ng panginoong Dyos ‘yan.” - INC Deacon</i></p>

3. Challenging Role	Personality and credibility of the leader was tested	<p><i>“Challenging. First PTA President in Marinduque from Buenavista. Una okay na lahat. Nag-shift lahat. Nasabi na sa tao need na baguhin. Tinitingnan din kasi ng tao kung may integridad ka, kakayahan. Pag nakita naman nila na may kakayahan ay susuportahan din nila. ‘Pag wala ay di rin sila naniniwala. Sa panahon naman natin ay sinusupportahan kita at kung hindi naman ay itutuloy pa rin naman. Determination. Integridad. Capability. Key determinants na binibigay ng sumusuporta o nasasakupan. Minsan ay iba-iba ang tingin ng mga tao. Perception nila yan.”</i> - Former PTA President</p>
4. Difficult	The duty requires time management and attention	<p><i>“Mahirap. Unang-una maya maya may padala, maya maya ang p.m ko dahil sa padala sa Palawan Pawnshop, kaya nanghingi na ko ng isang booklet ng resibo. Iniwan ko na lang tas binabalikan ko. Talagang busy. Talagang maayaw na ako. ‘Yung pagbayad ng lang ng quarterly ng BIR, wala namang pumapasok na pera. Bakit nagbabayad pa kami? One-year na kami hindi nagre-renew.”</i> - Alumni Treasurer</p>

The responses of beneficiaries, stakeholders, and members of implementing bodies were classified into three categories: significant, challenging, and difficult roles. Each role was deemed significant in the implementation of every ASP, with each contributor playing a vital part in the overall success. Out of the eight respondents queried, six identified their roles as significant. Senjaya (2019) emphasized that for schools to thrive, parents and community members must share ownership of the outcomes generated.

The school head, involved at all levels, initiates a root-cause analysis in collaboration with subject coordinators and relevant office personnel. They conceptualize potential ASPs to address identified issues, collaborating with concerned offices and tapping into various organizations and stakeholders as potential partners in project realization, alongside the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA), Student Government (SSG), and other relevant entities. Above all, the school head is accountable for every individual and activity within the school, ensuring accountability remains a primary duty.

“Accountability. Accountable ka sa lahat ng actions, situations, at undertakings at nangyayari sa project like BE.”, answered by the principal.

On the other hand, the former TIC has her strategy, *“It is worth it for the project. Taking the risk for the students, teachers, and school.”*

According to the former school head, it is one of the circumstances a school head must anticipate for a successful ASP.

For the BE Coordinator, as the school coordinator of BE, he serves only as the moderator. His main task is to inform the BE’s various committees regarding their assignments and functions.

“Kanya-kanya na sila. Ako lang ‘yung parang moderator. Transparency ang talagang reason bakit bumabalik-balik sila sa school. Kitang-kita ng nag-donate kung saan napupunta ang kanyang binigay.”

On the other hand, proper dissemination must be ensured, or all components will not function well.

Moreover, for all the ASPs, the active participation of the PTA Officers and SSG is always anticipated. They serve as the prime movers that keep the project working until it is accomplished. For the former SSG president to him his role,

“Very important din po dahil kung hindi namin na-facilitate ‘yung mga students kung saan madaan, mapunta ay malaking tulong na rin sa pag-concrete ng ground. Hindi na namroblema ‘yung mga workers sa pagsasabi sa mga students.”

The First PTA League President in the Division of Marinduque said that he was challenged due to the situation under Covid19.

“Challenging. First PTA President in Marinduque from Buenavista. Una okay na lahat. Nag-shift lahat. Nasabi na sa tao need na baguhin. Tinitingnan din kasi ng tao kung may integridad ka, kakayahan.”

The key determinants of a leader for others to support every project are determination, integrity, and capability are the key determinants of a leader for others to support every school project (Ahmed, 2018). Other parents are evaluating the tolerance and capacity of their leader. The SSG President, though minimal, did their best to manage their co-students to help during the project's implementation.

“Very important din po...Hindi na namroblema ‘yung mga workers sa pagsasabi sa mga students.”

A leader's position is critical in directing the many organizations providing services for the project's completion.

“Mahalaga sya sa planning at pagda-direct nung mga myembro.”

Moreover, for church-related organizations, recognition is to glorify God's name.

Muller (2018) highlighted that within voluntary groups, individuals with specific talents and qualifications often hold leadership positions, assuming responsibility for goal setting, decision-making, and serving as spokespersons. These leaders have elevated status, allowing them to guide other members, if followers accept this dynamic. To foster a sense of fulfillment conducive to effective teamwork and overall achievement, leaders must possess strong instincts regarding followers' expectations.

Massucco (2021) emphasized the importance of efficient communication tools, such as school apps, school messengers, text notifications, and electronic communication, for teachers and administrators. Regular updates on school events encourage greater parental involvement, promoting a stronger connection between the school and its stakeholders.

ChalkyPapers (2023) underscored the significance of collaborations between schools and communities, suggesting that such partnerships can yield fruitful outcomes in the

long term. This collaborative approach encourages stakeholders to engage more actively in school programs and provide additional support for learners.

Regarding volunteerism, Aranda et al. (2019) noted that motivations for volunteering vary, extending beyond altruism. Recent studies propose two motivational patterns - inward-oriented and outward-oriented - which correlate with volunteer satisfaction. Volunteers are more likely to feel valued, accepted, and satisfied in their roles when supported and supervised adequately by school members and stakeholders.

Table 18 shows how each respondent recounted in their statements the memorable moments they had experienced while contributing to every ASP of BNHS.

Table 18

Post-implementation Phase of the ASP in Terms of Remarkable Experiences Acquired

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Varied Remarkable Experiences	Significant experiences of the respondents about ASP differ from each other, but everything is worth remembering	<p><i>“Isang sabi lang sa alumni ay talagang nagapadala ng suporta agad. Pati mga PTA ay talagang masuporta. Kahit sino naman. Marami pating naga presenta.” (Smiling) - present principal</i></p> <p><i>“Yung pinarangalan ang BNHS as number 1 sa cluster tas second sa division. Sa loob ng sampung taon ay ngayon lang kita na-recognize. Sini-celebrate itong award na ito dahil pinagtulungan natin. The best na siguro ito ng pagiging coordinator. Pressured ngayong BE dahil baka iba naman kalabasan.” - BE Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Grabbing the opportunity offered by the alumni because it is a once in a lifetime opportunity for the benefit of the many and the coming generations.” - Former TIC</i></p> <p><i>“Masarap dahil nakakatulong.” - Alumni Treasurer</i></p> <p><i>“May inabigay na certificate ang school. Dinisplay ko sa extension ng kapilya sa Bicas-bicas. (Nakangiti) - INC Deacon</i></p> <p><i>“Yung malakas ang outsourcing ang remarkable experiences ko dahil masarap mag-report ‘pag maraming donations. Nakakalungkot pag akaunti.” - ASP Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Mahirap mag-invest sa isang programa lalo ‘pag involve ay pera. Public school at lahat ay hindi well-off. ‘Pag maganda ang project kahit mahirap ang buhay pinagkakaisahan. Walang maliit na ambag sa maliit na proyekto. Kaya namang mag-ambag sa pag-boluntaryo. Hindi man pera, malaki na rin.” - Former PTA Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“During the implementation po ay di magamit ang ground kapag flag ceremony ay may mga classrooms po na nasa dulo. Ang suggestion ng mga SSG ay lakasan ang mic or puntahan sa mga classrooms dahil hindi na rin po sila malabas ng room. Inisa-isa ng mga SSG sa mga classroom teachers.” - Former SSG President</i></p>

For the current principal, a significant moment was the consistent support received from the alumni. This support was demonstrated through prompt approval of requests after discussing issues with others, ensuring that no gap would go unfilled.

“Isang sabi lang sa alumni ay talagang nagapadala ng suporta agad. Pati mga PTA ay talagang masuporta. Kahit sino naman. Marami pating naga presenta.” (Smiling).

This justifies the experiences of the ASP School Coordinator, that the overflowing donations were her remarkable experience as a coordinator, making her feel delighted in encoding the donations in the database.

“Yung malakas ang outsourcing ang remarkable experiences ko dahil masarap mag-report ‘pag maraming donations.”

For the former principal,

“Grabbing the opportunity offered by the alumni because it is a once-in-a-lifetime opportunity for the benefit of the many and the coming generations.” was her outstanding experience.

Thinking of the more prolonged effects of the project. With similarities on the part of the School BE Coordinator,

“Yung pinarangalan ang BNHS as number 1 sa cluster tas second sa division. Sa loob ng sampung taon ay ngayon lang kita na-recognize. Sini-celebrate itong award na ito dahil pinagtulungan natin. The best na siguro ito ng pagiging coordinator.”

For the former PTA President, his remarkable experience was realizing the difficulty of investing in a program that involves money, especially in a public school with more not-so-well-off parents. He appreciated the willingness of each to share according to their abilities.

‘Pag maganda ang project kahit mahirap ang buhay pinagkakaisahan. Walang maliit na ambag sa maliit na proyekto. Kaya namang mag-ambag sa pag-boluntaryo. Hindi man pera, malaki na rin.”

For the former SSG President's remarkable experience, their effort of reaching out to students in each classroom for the announcements during the flag ceremony, which students could not attend due to the under-construction ground,
“Inisa-isa ng mga SSG ang mga classroom ng bawat teachers.”

This made him realize the importance of their role as SSG.

For the alumni representative, it is a good feeling that they were able to help others. They want to give back, reconnect and inspire, especially the young minds. Some also conveyed a sense of identity that linked them to both the school and the neighborhood and the desire to help, advise and inspire students.

Lastly, for the volunteer groups, awarding a certificate of recognition is well-appreciated because it recognizes their efforts for the services they rendered.

"Dinisplay ko sa extension ng kapilya sa Bicas-bicas.", stated the Deacon.

The instrumental role played by individuals in elevating BNHS to its current stature as a distinguished learning institution is remarkable.

According to *Why Volunteer/Inter* in Lakshyam (n.d.), volunteering is described as a simple yet effective and rewarding way to contribute to a cause that holds personal significance. The organization highlights several benefits of volunteering, including increased empathy towards others, enhanced confidence and overall personality development, and the potential to add value to one's resume, giving it a competitive edge. Volunteers believe that there is a sense of fulfilment and satisfaction in giving back to others rather than receiving.

These insights into volunteering have facilitated remarkable experiences for volunteers and school constituents, who purposefully dedicate their time to charitable endeavours. Volunteering serves as an effective tool for bringing people and communities together, empowering them, and fostering their capacities. As noted by Daniel et al. (2019), building relationships with diverse individuals in various settings outside the classroom is essential for learning, growth, and development.

Table 19 reflects how each Adopt-a-School Program was monitored during the implementation.

Table 19

Post-implementation Phase of the ASP in Terms of Monitoring of the ASP Implementation

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Well-monitored Project	The constant practice of monitoring the status of the project's implementation with documentation.	<p><i>"BE may monitor, may daily accomplishment report. HAFFMHE, meron din. Palagi nga ang update about the progress kaya lang hindi documented. Wala tayong general form para sa short-term ASP."</i> - Present Principal</p> <p><i>"Very light monitoring of the quality of project's implementation and quality."</i> - Former TIC</p> <p><i>"May monitoring at may mga forms po for each phase na ina-accomplish."</i> - BE Coordinator</p> <p><i>"May progress report po ay sa kanila na. Hindi ko po sakop 'yun."</i> - ASP Coordinator</p> <p><i>"Monitoring ay per year level na, per PTA Classroom President and Adviser. From time-to-time naman ay may natingin sa school, principal, teachers, officers, SSG."</i> - former PTA President</p> <p><i>"May naga monitoring maya maya ng progress ng trabaho ng mga brads from the school personnel."</i> - Tau Gamma Regent</p>

“Merong natingin-tingin. Maasikaso ang mga maestra. Tuwang-tuwa sila. Inaalam kung sapat ang mga gamit, kung nagmeryenda na kami.” - INC Deacon

“Nadalaw po nung engineer every now and then. May nakikita po ako natingin-tingin sa mga nagawa ng project.” - Former SSG President

“Meron po,” - Alumni Treasurer

Each phase of the project received consistent feedback from respondents, indicating that monitoring was conducted for each project. A monitoring form was utilized by the person in charge during monitoring activities to ensure periodic review of the project's status. Individuals responsible for monitoring included the principal, teachers, organization officers, and volunteers, with provisions made for refreshments during monitoring sessions.

In the Revised Implementing Rules and Guidelines of Republic Act (RA) No. 8525, also known as the Adopt-a-School Program Act or DepEd Order No. 2 Series of 2013, Part IV outlines program administration. Rule 1 Section d pertains to monitoring and evaluation of the program, albeit without specifying forms for utilization, unlike in the ASP BE.

Additionally, under DepEd Order No. 29, Series of 2022, which pertains to the Adoption of the Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (BEMEF), the school is designated as an accountable office responsible for providing directives and determining strategies to achieve agency performance targets, as defined in Section III. BNHS implemented monitoring for every ASP, either with a formatted monitoring form for DepEd or through alternative means, as confirmed by the present principal.

“BE may monitor, may daily accomplishment report. HAFFMHE, meron din. Palagi nga ang update about the progress kaya lang hindi documented. Wala tayong general form para sa short-term ASP.”

The BE Coordinator supported this statement of the principal.

“May monitoring at may mga forms po for each phase na ina-accomplish.”

Even the ASP Coordinator mentioned the progress report she observed, though this is not under her jurisdiction.

“May progress report po, ay sa kanila na. Hindi ko po sakop ‘yun.”

The implementation of BNHS' ASPs demonstrated a clear embrace of School-Based Management (SBM), as indicated by respondents' statements. This approach, as highlighted in the Consumer Guide from the Office of Research and Education, has the potential to enhance learning environments for students by engaging teachers, parents, and community members in critical decision-making processes (Llego, n.d.).

Through the transfer of significant decision-making authority and empowerment of various school components, stakeholder involvement progressively increased as they recognized the significance of their contributions to the educational system.

The former PTA President affirmed the monitoring of the project, underscoring the commitment to overseeing ASP implementation.

“Monitoring ay per year level na, per PTA Classroom President and Adviser. From time-to-time naman ay may natingin sa school, principal, teachers, officers, SSG.”

The Tau Gamma Regent’s statement was paralleled to the statement of the former PTA President.

“May naga monitoring maya maya ng progress ng trabaho ng mga brads from the school personnel.”

On the part of the INC Deacon, he emphasized the active monitoring by the teachers.

“Merong natingin-tingin. Maasikaso ang mga maestra. Tuwang-tuwa sila. Inaalam kung sapat ang mga gamit, kung nagmeryenda na kami.”

The former SSG President shared his observations on the participation of the other volunteers.

“Nadalaw po nung engineer every now and then. May nakikita po ako natingin-tingin sa mga nagawa ng project.”

Even the alumni representative observed the same circumstances.

“Meron po.”

Monitoring of forms for BE were submitted to the Division Office during the nominations of BNHS in the Division of Marinduque for Best Brigada Implementer.

Table 20 presents the statements of the respondents on how the ASPs were evaluated after its implementation.

Table 20

Post-implementation Phase of the Adopt-a-School Program in Terms of Evaluation of the Project After the Implementation

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. Evaluated	The last action that an ASP must attain after it has been accomplished	<p><i>“BE, may evaluation form ang Brigada.”</i> - Present Principal</p> <p><i>“Internal evaluation from the BNHS Faculty”</i> - Former TIC</p> <p><i>“May evaluation form at narrative reports.”</i> - BE Coordinator</p>
	This serves as the determinant in the re-implementation and	<p><i>“May evaluation po ng mga projects.”</i> - Tau Gamma Regent</p>

	termination of the ASP.	<i>"Inatingnan nila kung okay na ang trabaho, kung maayos o may aayusin pa."</i> - INC Deacon
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
		<i>"Opo. During LAC session, tinatanong ang feedback from the teachers at kung ano ang sinabi na nakarating sa teachers. Positive ang common feedbacks like sa HAFFMHE, send-off tuwang-tuwa ang mga players, early pregnancy ay kasali ang JHS Grade 10. Concreting ay okay lang kaso feedback mali, na inuna muna dapat ang drainage bago concrete ground."</i> - ASP Coordinator
2. Not Evaluated	Evaluation was not observed by the other respondents	<p><i>"Wala. Ang mahalagang evaluation dyan ay 'yung mga tao. Makikita ang effectiveness ay dahil hindi na sila napuputikan."</i> - Former PTA President</p> <p><i>"Wala po. Umalis na rin si President. Nag-online na lang siguro sila sa evaluation and endorsement."</i> - Alumni Treasurer</p> <p><i>"Wala po akong alam na evaluation 'nung project. Hindi kami pinatawag. Siguro po ay sa dating TIC."</i> - Former SSG President</p>

To enhance future projects, it is crucial to conduct a thorough analysis of the project, focusing on areas where mistakes were made, and improvements can be implemented. Each project should serve as a learning opportunity for the team, allowing them to assess its success and areas for improvement (Florida Tech, 2018).

The ASPs of BNHS were divided into two categories for this phase: evaluated and not evaluated, based on respondents' statements. Most respondents confirmed that the school's ASPs were evaluated, with only three indicating otherwise.

While some respondents mentioned being unaware or unable to participate in the evaluation process due to absence, and one respondent had their own method of evaluation, it was evident that a definite evaluation was conducted for each project.

The present principal confirmed the availability of evaluation forms and narrative reports for the Brigada Eskwela (BE) projects. For ASPs, evaluation was conducted through feedback from various stakeholders due to the lack of a specific evaluation form for this purpose.

"May evaluation form at narrative reports."

This was seconded by the BE Coordinator, *"Opo. During LAC session, tinatanong ang feedback from the teachers at kung ano ang sinabi na nakarating sa teachers. Positive ang common feedback like sa HAFFMHE, send-off tuwang-tuwa ang mga players, early pregnancy ay kasali ang JHS Grade 10."*, reiteration of the School Adopt-a-School Program Coordinator.

Feedbacking of the ASPs were done anchored to Table 15, Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework Section VIII Roles and Responsibilities of Offices body evaluated its ASPs, as suggested by the framework in school-based sessions during LAC sessions and after each ASP. Results were discussed and properly disseminated to the stakeholders during the General PTA Meeting.

If the ASP does not have an evaluation form, as most ASPs listed below do, internal and external evaluations were made during the LAC session cited by the ASP Coordinator.

“Positive ang common feedback like sa HAFFMHE, send-off tuwang-tuwa ang mga players, early pregnancy ay kasali ang JHS Grade 10. Concreting ay okay lang kaso ang feedback mali, na inuna muna dapat ang drainage bago concrete ground.”

The Tau Gamma Regent confidently stated,

“May evaluation po ng mga projects.”

For the other group of volunteers,

“Inatingnan nila kung okay na ang trabaho, kung maayos o may aayusin pa.”

The recipients, donors, and implementing organizations of the implemented ASP made evaluations based on their comments and feedback.

According to the previous TIC of the school,

“Internal evaluation from the BNHS Faculty”

Although most of the key personalities were informed about the evaluation, there were some officers of the school bodies who were not.

“Wala po. Umalis na rin si President. Nag-online na lang siguro sila sa evaluation and endorsement.”

The respondent, who is the current Treasurer of the alumni, was not notified about the review of the project,

“Wala po akong alam na evaluation ‘nung project. Hindi kami pinatawag. Siguro po ay sa dating TIC.”

The SSG was not told about the internal appraisal of the project's concreting. However, the SSG Adviser among the faculty members for most of the ASPs represented their organization.

The former PTA President viewed his way of evaluating an accomplishment,

“Wala. Ang mahalagang evaluation dyan ay ‘yung mga tao. Makikita ang effectiveness ay dahil hindi na sila napuputikan.”

As part of their responsibilities, faculty members evaluated the services and scope of work of volunteer organizations.

Eby (2022) emphasized that any evaluation worth undertaking should ultimately save a school time and money while producing better results. Evaluation serves as a mechanism for documenting outcomes and facilitating improvement, enabling others to learn from both successes and failures. This process facilitates the efficient allocation of limited time and resources (FloridaTech, 2018). Moreover, it provides guidance for all activities undertaken by the school administration committee, allowing for modification and enhancement of educational initiatives.

The present principal noted the absence of a monitoring and evaluation form for short-term ASPs in Table 19 but intends to develop one for school-based monitoring and evaluation in the next year of ASP implementation.

In order to improve on the next project, it is important to analyze the project and concentrate on the areas where it went wrong and made mistakes. Each project should allow the team to improve as it assesses its success (Florida Tech, 2018).

The ASPs of BNHS were categorized into two for this phase: evaluated and not evaluated, as evident in the statements of the respondents. Most of them confirmed that the ASPs of the school were being evaluated. Only three responded as not evaluated.

Although some of the respondents commented that they were not aware or failed to evaluate the ASP due to their absence from the process and one of them had his own way of evaluating, a definite evaluation was made for each project.

The evaluation form and narrative report for BE were available, as confirmed by the present principal of the school. For ASP, evaluation was through feedback of the different components due to the lack of a specific evaluation form for this.

“May evaluation form at narrative reports.”

This was seconded by the BE Coordinator,

“Opo. During LAC session, tinatanong ang feedback from the teachers at kung ano ang sinabi na nakarating sa teachers. Positive ang common feedback like sa HAFFMHE, send-off tuwang-tuwa ang mga players, early pregnancy ay kasali ang JHS Grade 10.”, reiteration of the school adopt-a school program coordinator.

Feedbacking of the ASPs were done anchored to *Table 15*, Basic Education Monitoring and Evaluation Framework Section VIII Roles and Responsibilities of Offices body evaluated its ASPs as suggested by the framework in school-based sessions during LAC sessions and after each ASP. Results were discussed and properly disseminated to the stakeholders during the General PTA Meeting.

If the ASP does not have an evaluation form, as most ASPs listed below do, internal and external evaluations were made during the LAC session cited by the ASP Coordinator.

“Positive ang common feedback like sa HAFFMHE, send-off tuwang-tuwa ang mga players, early pregnancy ay kasali ang JHS Grade 10. Concreting ay okay lang kaso ang feedback mali, na inuna muna dapat ang drainage bago concrete ground.”

The Tau Gamma Regent confidently stated,

“May evaluation po ng mga projects.”

For the other group of volunteers,

“Inatingnan nila kung okay na ang trabaho, kung maayos o may aayusin pa.”

The recipients, donors, and implementing organizations of the implemented ASP made evaluations based on their comments and feedback.

According to the previous TIC of the school,

“Internal evaluation from the BNHS Faculty”

Although most of the key personalities were informed about the evaluation, there were some officers of the school bodies who were not.

“Wala po. Umalis na rin si President. Nag-online na lang siguro sila sa evaluation and endorsement.”

The respondent, who is the current Treasurer of the alumni, was not notified about the review of the project,

“Wala po akong alam na evaluation ‘nung project. Hindi kami pinatawag. Siguro po ay sa dating TIC.”

The SSG was not told about the internal appraisal of the project's concreting. However, the SSG Adviser among the faculty members for the majority of the ASPs represented their organization.

The former PTA President viewed his way of evaluating an accomplishment, *“Wala. Ang mahalagang evaluation dyan ay ‘yung mga tao. Makikita ang effectivenessn ay dahil hindi na sila napuputikan.”*

As assigned to them, faculty members evaluated the volunteer organizations' services and scope of work.

Eby (2022) reiterated that any evaluation that is worthwhile must ultimately save a school's time and money and yield better results. It offers a mechanism to chronicle results and a means of improvement so that others can learn from one's achievements and failures. This allows for the efficient delegation of limited time and resources (FloridaTech, 2018). Additionally, it provides direction for everything the school administration committee does while modifying and enhancing educational initiatives.

The present principal mentioned the unavailability of a monitoring and evaluation form for short-term ASP in Table 19 but will attempt to formulate one for school-based M&E in the next year of ASP implementation.

Assistance from Donors to Support ASP Implementation

This phase will discuss the provisions extended by the sponsors or partner groups, agencies and organizations in accomplishing the different ASPs of BNHS as allowed forms of assistance stated in R.A. 8525 extracted from the statements of the respondents during the face-to-face interview.

Table 21 includes the statements of the participants related to the provided forms of assistance for each ASPs.

Table 21

Common Form of Assistance According to Adopt-a-School Program

Theme	Definition	Common Responses
1. In-kind donation and services	Form of support resources that mostly extended to BNHS by partner agencies or organizations, donors, and stakeholders	<p><i>“Alumni: services, t-shirts, construction materials. Malaking percentage ang service.” - BNHS ASP School Coordinator</i></p> <p><i>“Ang nakita ko po sa concreting ay mga equipments, provided nila, yung materials at workers.” - Former SSG President</i></p> <p><i>“Labor; mason, carpentry, painters and clearing of school grounds.” - INC Deacon</i></p> <p><i>“Usually, po ay in terms of human resources, labor, ganyan kung ano-ano.” - Tau Gamma Leader</i></p> <p><i>“Learners’ support. Readily available like electric fan, pagkain. Kadalasan ay madaling mapakinabangan. Mga short terms. Culture of volunteerism and gift-giving.</i></p> <p><i>Wala masyadong long term like pa-training mula sa stakeholders. Time, materials, labor ang kadalasan nilang inabigay. May mga long-term effect din siguro sa mga bata na di malimutan.” - Present BNHS Principal</i></p> <p><i>“Maraming nagdo-donate. Yung mga maliliit na stakeholders ay nagbibigay ng certain amount: pa meryenda, bakery ay tinapay. May malalaking establishments like hardware ay pintura, paint brush, tinner, yero. Ang mga alumni ay cash donations.” - BE School Coordinator</i></p>
	Consumable learning-support assistance and services for the learners that requires DOD but does not require MOA	

The Buenavista National High School (BNHS) Adopt-a-School Program (ASP) and Corresponding Forms of Assistance outlined various types of assistance available, with most forms being short-term, except for the concreting of school grounds. The forms of assistance provided include cash, health and sanitation supplies, food supplies, school supplies, t-shirts, electric fans, television, training, and orientation. These forms of assistance are all covered by ASP Act provisions.

During document review, it was observed that the common form of assistance received by BNHS, as reflected in the ASPs, primarily consisted of in-kind forms of assistance,

with services being the predominant type. Respondents uniformly classified assistance in a similar manner.

In the case of Brigada Eskwela (BE), labor comprised the largest percentage of assistance, as indicated by data presented in Table 5, which outlines forms of assistance and service with monetary equivalents and the number of partners for school years 2019-2022.

The ASP Coordinator affirmed this observation during the interview, further substantiated by Table 21, which details the common forms of assistance according to the Adopt-a-School Program.

“Malaking percentage ang service. Usually, po ay in terms of human resources, labor, ganyan kung ano-anu.”

The Tau Gamma representative and the INC Deacon elaborated on the specific forms of labor rendered, including masons, carpenters, painters, electricians, plumbers, welders, and helpers.

In-kind donations were prevalent during short-term ASPs. According to Jitasa (2021), in-kind donations refer to the transfer of assets, goods, products, or services provided by individuals, organizations, or businesses, which are non-monetary contributions made to nonprofit organizations. These donations vary according to the needs of the learners pursued in the ASPs.

The DepEd ASP Toolkit states that stakeholders can choose from a menu of options called packages within the software. These packages encompass various initiatives such as the construction of new school facilities, libraries, computer labs, staff development, nutrition programs, and the supply of instructional materials and learning kits. This approach ensures that the demands of the school are met in alignment with the capabilities and goals of the business sector.

The statements of the respondents further justified the forms of in-kind donations.

“Learners’ support. Readily available like electric fan, pagkain. Kadalasan ay madaling mapakinabangan.”

Moreover, the BE coordinator said that some stakeholders contribute in terms of food and cash donations.

“Yung mga maliliit na stakeholders ay nagbibigay ng certain amount: pa meryenda, bakery ay tinapay. May malalaking establishments like hardware ay pintura, paint brush, tinner, yero. Ang mga alumni ay cash donations.”

According to the former SSG President on concreting of the school ground,

“Ang nakita ko po sa concreting ay mga equipments, provided nila, yung materials at workers.”

Corroborated by the current principal and reflected in the ASPs provided herein are rare donations for the long term.

“Wala masyadong long term like pa-training mula sa stakeholders. Time, materials, labor ang kadalasan nilang inabigay. May mga long-term effect din siguro sa mga bata na di malimutan.”

Table 22 projects the different Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National High School and the various forms of assistance provided by the ASPs to the beneficiaries

Table 22

Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National High School and The Corresponding Forms of Assistance Provided

ADOPT-A-SCHOOL PROGRAMS OF BNHS						
		Send-Off Program for Provincial Players	Forum on Teenage-Pregnancy and Early Marriage	HAFFMHE	Concreting of BNHS School Ground	Brigada Eskwela
FORMS OF ASSISTANCE PROVIDED FOR THE ASP	Learning Environment				CHB, Corrugated Metal, Cement, Tie Wire, Labor	Labor, Electric Fan, Sinks
	Learning support					School Supplies
	Technology Support					Television
	Health and Nutrition	Foods and Health Supplies	Reproductive Health Awareness & Snacks	Food Supplies		Health & Sanitation Supplies, Clothes
	Reading Program					Books
	Training and Development	Orientation of Provincial Players		Parenting Seminar		
	Direct Assistance	Cash Assistance for MIMAROPA RAA Players				
	Assistive Learning Devices for Students with Special Needs					Eyeglasses

Source: Junior High School and Senior High School Guidance Offices

The form of assistance provided varies per project to address the specific needs of learners, ultimately benefiting parents and teachers as well.

The ASP Send Off Program for Players aims to offer moral support and assistance to the Buenavista district delegation in the annual Provincial Meet. Provisions include food and health supplies, player orientation, and cash assistance for MIMAROPARAA players.

The Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage focuses on raising awareness about reproductive health to reduce cases of teenage pregnancies and early marriages. Program provisions include reproductive health lectures and snacks for participants and speakers.

The Healing and Firming for a More Holistic Education (HAFFMHE) program facilitates communication between the school and student families to enhance understanding and collaboration for an optimal learning environment. The program provides responsible parenthood lectures and addresses basic family needs.

Brigada Eskwela (BE) is an annual program consisting of short-term and long-term assistance based on donor or sponsor provisions, covering various ASP provisions.

The Concreting of the School Grounds aims to enhance school facilities and promote students' physical and socio-emotional well-being through school activities. Provisions include sacks of cement, corrugated steel, labor, and a mixer.

HAFFMHE and Concreting of the School Grounds are one-time implementation projects, with the possibility of HAFFMHE being re-implemented depending on project outcomes.

In each ASP, BNHS aims for longer-term effects to improve learners' lives and foster community advancement.

Effects of the Adopt-a-School Programs on the School's Performance

This section examines the outcomes of the various ASPs implemented by BNHS, alongside the school's performance as indicated by figures in the School Report Card. It delves into the effects of the distinct ASPs on beneficiaries and evaluates the effectiveness of projects and programs based on beneficiary appreciation and perception.

As suggested by Eby (2022), reviewing the project scope, assessing project requirements, examining the project budget, and gauging client and internal satisfaction are key methods for evaluating project success.

The initial components of BNHS' ASPs were discussed in earlier sections of this paper. The subsequent statements from beneficiaries assess whether project interventions under BNHS' ASPs have led to longer-term impacts and sustainable changes for beneficiaries and, eventually, target extension beneficiaries, as indicated in the SRC and in respondent statements.

These assessments include positive effects on beneficiaries, whether emotional or intellectual, as articulated during interviews. They also aim to determine whether intended problems have been successfully addressed. Ultimately, successful implementation of BNHS' ASPs will be reflected in the emulation of BNHS' ASPs by other institutions.

Based on the Perception of the Participants

The various Adopt-a-School Programs at Buenavista National High School were reviewed and assessed by the respondents based on their perceptions. This includes the advantages and disadvantages of implementing the ASP. The benefits of the participants being beneficiaries of the ASP were highlighted. Likewise, the impressions and reactions of the respondents during the face-to-face interview were taken into consideration because the researcher believes that these have great impacts on the credibility of the project's success.

Table 23 reflects the efforts of the school implementing body in conducting the different Adopt-a-School Programs based on the statements of the beneficiaries of the programs.

Table 23

Efforts of the school through its Adopt-a-School Programs

Send Off Program for Players		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Reached out and inspired sports delegation members	The main objective of the Send Off Program for Players	<p><i>"Nagulat po ako, kami 'nung ina-nounce na may send-off program. Nakaka-touch naman po ang mga sinabi ng mga guro sa programa bago mag distribute ng goody bags. Naisip ko first time na nangyari ito sa akin, yung maramdaman ko ang suporta ng lahat, hindi lang ng coach. Sabi ko, Wow! Kailangan kong maging best player."</i> (Smiling. Overwhelmed).</p> <p><i>"Mas na-inspired po akong makipag-compete sa Provincial at MIMAROPARAA dahil naiisip ko nakakahiya naman na todo suporta ang mga guro, magulang at buong Buenavista tapos hindi ko abigay 'yung the best ko.</i></p> <p><i>Bilang player mas disiplinado po ako dahil naisip ko hindi lang pangalan ko o ng event namin ang dala ko, kundi buong bayan ng Buenavista. Sabi ko 'pag nakapagtapos ako at nagka trabaho, ako naman ang susuporta sa mga players."</i> - Provincial and two-time Basketball MIMAROPARAA player</p> <p><i>"Malaki po ang naitulong ng send-off programs for players ng BNHS. Mas ginanahan po akong makipag-compete sa bawat event. Mas pinaunlad nito ang bawat manlalaro ng BNHS.</i></p> <p><i>Masaya po dahil mas na-inspire ang mga manlalaro ng BNHS. Naibigay nila ang tulong panganagilangan ng mga players."</i> - Taekwondo Player - Provincial Silver Medalist</p> <p><i>"Unang-una natuwa ako dahil coach, ako ay natuwa dahil may tumugon sa pangangailangan ng aming mga players.</i></p> <p><i>Ganun pa man at nakakahiya na dapat ang coach o teacher ay mag-provide ng sarili nilang panganagilangan, nakakatuwa dahil kasama ang mga coaches sa binigyan ng tulong.</i></p> <p><i>Ang alam ko pong focus ng programa ay BNHS lang. Subalit dahil mahusay ang nag-organisa ng proyekto at pilantropo ang mga sponsors. Ako po'y lubos ang kagalakan na ang buong cluster ng Buenavista ay nabibiyayaan ng ganitong programa. Sana po sa sunod pa ay higit duon at hindi lamang high school kundi kasama na rin ang elementarya."</i> - BNHS PESS Coordinator and Coach</p>

Healing and Firming Families for a More Holistic Education (HAFFMHE)		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses

Realization and Appreciation of Parental Roles	<p>The beneficiary parent realized her role as a parent through the ASP of the school.</p> <p>The beneficiary appreciated the effort made by the school by holding the ASP.</p>	<p><i>“Malaki ang naitulong. Naibahagi ang konting pangangailangan ng aming mag-ina tulad ng spaghetti, bigas, sardinas, gatas, kape, asukal, noodles at mga biscuits.”</i></p> <p><i>“Masaya po ako. Napa-aga ang punta ko sa school. Naisip ko na dapat maaga at mapila pa para makapirma sa attendance. Sinabihan ko mga anak ko na mag-aral mabuti at ‘pag sila sy nakatapos at naging maayos ang buhay ay sila naman ang matulong sa iba.”</i></p> <p><i>“Nagapasalamat ako at napasama sa mga nakatanggap. Ito pa naman ‘yung panahon na walang-wala kami dahil sa dami ng gastos ‘ nung na hospital at namatay ang asawa ko.” (Naiiyak na nagsasalita. Garalgal ang boses) - widowed</i></p> <p><i>“Mas na-appreciate ko ang pag-aral dahil may mga taong gustong tumulong sa amin kahit papano.”</i></p> <p><i>“Masaya dahil napasama sa nabigyan ng mga biyaya.” - orphaned</i></p>
Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage Forum		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Self-realization and awareness	The beneficiary realized something after benefiting from the ASP	<p><i>“Natutunan at nalaman ko ang mga maaaring mangyari kapag naging isang batang ina. Ipinakita ‘dun ‘yung mga posibleng mangyari kapag ma-aga ang pagbubuntis.</i></p> <p><i>Naisip ko sana hindi mangyari sa akin ‘yun. Pero sa hirap ng buhay ay hindi rin naiwasan.</i></p> <p><i>Na-realize ko na tama at maganda ang mga ipinakita ni Dra. sa mga videos dahil ‘yung iba nasubok lang nang nasubok hindi naisip ang akalabasan ng kanilang ginagawa” - Former student of BNHS who attended the forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage</i></p> <p><i>“Nagkaroon ako ng self-realization at self- awareness about sa teenage pregnancy. Natutunan ko kung paano ba ito maiiwasan at ‘yung mga kaakibat na responsibility if ever na mangyari ito. Malaki ang impact nito sa pagkatao ko ngayon dahil naging mulat ako sa reyalidad ng buhay . . . mapalad ako dahil isa ako sa mga mag-aaral na nabigyan ng pagkakataong mauto at maging bukas ang kaisipan patungkol sa isyung ito.”- Former student of BNHS who attended the forum and was hailed as 2022 Miss World Tourism Philippines</i></p>

In every ASP launched by BNHS, beneficiaries reported feeling inspired, challenged, appreciated, and realizing new insights, as reflected in interview statements. These effects stem from the diligent efforts of the implementing bodies, consistent donor support, and contributions from all involved in realizing each project. The positive outcomes following each program's implementation have motivated BNHS and its implementing bodies to continue pursuing their objectives through annual implementation.

Dumpit (2021) assured a strong correlation between school improvement and community involvement, noting that increased school improvement results from both community involvement and the Adopt-A-School Program. Organizations adopting BNHS programs benefit from positive public relations through their engagement with a critical community component. Lubienski et al. (2018) confirmed that schools benefit from this involvement, as students gain enrichment from programs that expand their knowledge base, and school staff and faculty receive necessary support.

Interviewee responses highlighted their appreciation and recognition of BNHS's efforts, particularly for the Send Off Program, which motivated players to excel and increased the number of awards received by the school and district in the Provincial Meet. A former Provincial and two-time Basketball MIMAROPAARAA player expressed his overwhelming appreciation for the program during its first implementation, underscoring the program's positive impact on the participants.

"Nagulat po ako, kami 'nung ina-nounce na may send-off program. Nakakatouch naman po ang mga sinabi ng mga guro sa programa bago mag distribute ng goody bags. Naisip ko first time na nangyari ito sa akin, yung maramdaman ko ang suporta ng lahat, hindi lang ng coach."

Another athlete, the former Taekwondo Provincial Medalist, made a positive comment about the program.

"Malaki po ang naitulong ng send-off program for players ng BNHS. Mas ginanahan po akong makipag-compete sa bawat event. Mas pinaunlad nito ang bawat manlalaro ng BNHS."

According to Amaro (2020), engaging in high school athletics offers enduring and indisputable advantages, particularly when athletic administrators foster a climate that both encourages and tests the growth attitude. When individuals receive this kind of help, they form behaviors that last into high school.

One of the players said,

"Sabi ko, Wow! Kailangan kong maging MVP." (face lighted).

The players were even reminding themselves to be more disciplined because of what they heard from the speakers during the send-off program. Moreover, they pledged themselves to do the same thing.

"Bilang player mas disiplinado po ako dahil naisip ko hindi lang pangalan ko o ng event namin ang dala ko, kundi buong bayan ng Buenavista."

One of them said,

"Sabi ko 'pag nakapagtapos ako at nagka trabaho, ako naman ang susuporta sa mga players."

The unanticipated domino effect of the program on the players and the community was a success on the part of BNHS.

Beneficiary players of the Send-Off Program claimed the success of the program by the changes and realizations they had based on their experiences in the ASP. They felt the community's enthusiastic support gave them a hard push to do their best during the provincial meet, thinking the entire district of Buenavista was competing with them.

Even one of the coaches appreciated the efforts extended by BNHS to the players.

“Unang-una natuwa ako dahil coach ako. Ako ay natuwa dahil may tumugon sa pangangailangan ng aming mga players.”

On the other hand, the School PESS Coordinator and coach were both delighted and inspired by the effort extended, which benefited both the players and the coaches. This positive outcome was contrary to the coach's initial expectation that only BNHS players would benefit. The program's benefits were extended to include not only the BNHS coaches but also the coaches and players from secondary schools throughout the entire district. This broader impact underscored the program's inclusive and far-reaching influence, contributing to a more comprehensive and supportive environment for all participants involved in the district's athletic programs.

“Ang alam ko pong focus ng programa ay BNHS lang. Subalit dahil mahusay ang nag-organisa ng proyekto at pilantropo ang mga sponsors, ako po'y lubos ang kagalakan na ang buong cluster ng Buenavista ay nabibiyayaan ng ganitong programa. Sana po sa sunod pa ay higit duon at hindi lamang high school kundi kasama na rin ang elementarya.”

The PESS Coordinator expressed a desire for the program to be extended to the entire district in the next year of its implementation. This wish was realized the following year when the district supervisor aimed to benefit the delegation of the entire district. Amaro (2020) emphasized that schools providing athletic opportunities and support help players and students maintain lifelong habits. The progressive achievements in the Provincial Meet and the athletes' positive evaluations of the ASP reflect the value they place on the support extended to them. This support leaves a lasting impact on their lives, as they remember being encouraged and supported during their competitive years.

For the ASP Healing and Firming for a More Holistic Education (HAFFMHE) beneficiaries, the program was successful due to the realization of parental roles and the appreciation expressed by parents. This activity aimed to bridge the connection between the school and special members of the parent community, such as solo parents, widowed parents, and orphaned students. Dagupon and Garin (2022) define a solo parent as someone who lives alone or without a partner, raising a child or children on their own. In most cases, this role is taken up by mothers.

ChalkyPapers (2023) explained that the partnership between the community and the school benefits both sides. Schools significantly impact neighborhoods by meeting the critical need for local children's education. As a result, communities can help schools establish mutually beneficial relationships, creating a positive learning environment and helping students internalize values and cultural norms. One of the intangible contributions of BNHS to the community through this ASP is that parents became more inspired to do their best for their children, working both as mother and father.

Overall, the involvement of the community in supporting ASPs like HAFFMHE fostered a more inclusive and supportive environment, encouraging parents to take an active role in their children's education and well-being. This collaboration between the school and the

community is essential for creating a nurturing environment that benefits students and their families.

A separated parent said,

“Para po sa akin ay successful ang programa. Mas na-appreciate ko po ‘yung mga anak ko. Na kahit walang suporta ang ama nila ay mas na-appreciate ko malasakit ng BNHS. Naiisip pa nila ang mga kalagayan ng bawat estudyante bukod pa sa aturo nila.”

Another indicator of the programs’ success was the intangible contribution to the parents that they felt being challenged because of what BNHS did for their children and being thankful for having been included among the beneficiaries.

“Successful po ang programa. Mas na-realize ko bilang magulang na dapat mas magsikap ako. Kung ibang tao nga may malasakit sa amin dapat mas may malasakit kami sa myembro ng pamilya.”

“Hindi ko po inaasahan na ako po’y mapasama sa ganung programa para sa mga single parents sa BNHS. Kaya ako po’y nagapasalamat”

This activity had a profound impact on one of the parents because when the activity occurred, it was weeks right after the death of her husband. The widow said,

“Ito pa naman ‘yung panahon na walang-wala kami dahil sa dami ng gastos ‘nung nasa hospital at namatay ang asawa ko.” (Crying talking. The voice was scratchy).

“Malaki ang naitulong. Naibahagi ang konting pangangailangan ng aming mag-ina tulad ng spaghetti, bigas, sardinas, gatas, kape, asukal, noodles at mga biscuits.”

The widowed encouraged her children to do the same once they succeeded in life.

“Masaya po ako...Sinabihan ko mga anak ko na mag-aral mabuti at ‘pag sila ay nakatapos at naging maayos ang buhay ay sila naman ang matulong sa iba.”

The statement of the widowed parent strongly supports Little (n.d.) that everyone gains when educational institutions and neighborhood organizations collaborate to enhance learning. Partnerships truly help to increase program quality, make better use of resources, and better align goals and curricula by strengthening, supporting, and even transforming individual partners.

Not only the parents were able to appreciate the program, but also the children.

“Mas na-appreciate ko ang pag-aral dahil may mga taong gustong tumulong sa amin kahit papano. Masaya dahil napasama sa nabigyan ng mga biyaya.”

The program may not have fully met the beneficiaries' needs, but it provided them with assistance that was deeply appreciated for its purposes and intentions. Dumpit (2021) acknowledged that the government and schools might not be able to offer a straight remedy without outside help. Therefore, the school head must ensure that partnerships and volunteerism in schools through community participation are crucial to maintaining and raising the standard of public education.

Regarding the beneficiaries of the Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage Forum, the realization on their part is the best indicator that proved the program's success. The forum made them fully aware of their reproductive health and related topics, helping them become sexually responsible individuals and parents someday. This initiative by BNHS could help reduce the worldwide cases of unplanned pregnancies. Nearly half of pregnancies worldwide are unplanned, and over 218 million women lack access to birth control. There are many innovative instances of advancement in reducing the unmet need for family planning, promoting gender equity, and lowering birth rates, from Guatemala to Kenya and the Philippines (Peluso, 2023).

One of the beneficiaries, who became a mother at an early age months after attending the forum, admitted that she was informed about the consequences but ironically failed to practice what she heard. The realization came after facing the results of her actions. This underscores the importance of such forums in providing critical information and the ongoing need for support and education to help young individuals make informed decisions.

The Teen Pregnancy and Early Marriage Forum highlights the importance of continuous education and support. While the immediate impact might not be visible for all attendees, the long-term benefits and the gradual shift in awareness and behavior can contribute to reducing teenage pregnancies and promoting responsible sexual behavior. This aligns with global efforts to address unplanned pregnancies and improve reproductive health education.

“Successful po ang programa. Natutunan at nalaman ko ang mga maaaring mangyari kapag naging isang batang ina. Ipinakita ‘dun ‘yung mga posibleng mangyari kapag maaaga ang pagbubuntis.

“Na-realize ko na tama at maganda ang mga ipinakita ni Doktora sa mga videos dahil ‘yung iba nasubok lang nang nasubok hindi naiisip ang akalabasan ng kanilang ginagawa”, she uttered with hesitation on her face.

Though there was regret on her part, realization was the only thing that was left.

“Naisip ko sana hindi mangyari sa akin ‘yun. Pero sa hirap ng buhay ay hindi rin naiwasan,” she added.

Unlike the other beneficiary, a former student of BNHS who attended the forum and was hailed as the 2022 Miss World Tourism Philippines, realized the possible outcomes right before she got involved into a difficult situation. She directly stated,

“Para po sa akin ay successful ang programa. Nagkaroon ako ng self-realization at self-awareness about sa teenage pregnancy. Natutunan ko kung paano ba ito maiiwasan at ‘yung mga kaakibat na responsibility if ever na mangyari ito. Malaki ang impact nito sa pagkatao ko ngayon dahil naging mulat ako sa reyalidad ng buhay.”

“Para sa akin, mapalad ako dahil isa ako sa mga mag-aaral na nabigyan ng pagkakataong matuto at maging bukas ang kaisipan patungkol sa isyung ito.” (Smiling.)

Her appreciation for learning about life through attending the ASP on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage was evident in her smile. This program not only addresses the current conditions of the beneficiaries but also impacts their future. Khan et al. (2019) emphasized that young adults' reproductive health involves their ability to recognize and manage risks and implications associated with it. A girl's adolescent experiences significantly influence her life and the lives of her family members.

The beneficiaries confirmed during face-to-face interviews that the ASPs of BNHS positively contributed not only to the learners but also to their families and community members. This feedback highlights the far-reaching impact of the programs, which extend beyond immediate educational outcomes to broader social and familial benefits. It can be inferred that if families benefited from the programs, community therefore benefited in the implementation of the ASPs.

The BNHS ASPs have shown that well-designed and thoughtfully implemented programs can create a ripple effect, fostering a supportive environment for learners, their families, and the wider community. These initiatives not only enhance educational experiences but also contribute to the holistic development of individuals, equipping them with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate various life challenges.

School and community partnerships can provide students today with a better education and help with the demands put on the schools to meet expectations set by the Department of Education. Through communities in schools, students can have access to resources that can help them succeed in school. The benefits of community and school partnerships are numerous. The community can support educators in an ever-evolving world where there is increased pressure on them to ensure that pupils meet high standards of excellence.

Table 24 contains the statements of the participant beneficiaries of the programs justifying that the problems affecting the learning of the students were remedied by the Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National high School.

Table 24

Adopt-a-School Programs Addressed the Problems

Send-off Program for Players		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Problem addressed	The ASP was able to remedy, solve and give solution to the problem	<p><i>“Opp. Malaking bagay sa isang player ‘yung may basic needs ka ng baon papunta sa competition katulad ng shampoo, sabon, toothpaste, toothbrush, deodorant, medyas, face towel, biscuit, milo energen at gatorade. Nakakabawas bigat sa isipin ng player ‘yung mga pangangailangang ganun. ‘Pag MIMAROPARAA nga po ay may cash allowance pa ako.” (Somewhat like surprised by the added assistance as a regional player) - Provincial and MIMAROPARAA Player</i></p> <p><i>“Opp. Dahil binigyan din po kami ng dagdag kaalaman at impormasyon bago pa mag-distribute ng mga goody bags. Nabibigyan ng karagdagang pangangailangan ang mga manlalaro.” - Taekwondo Player</i></p>

		<i>"Naniniwala po ako na nakatugon ito pero yung' sasabihin po natin na 100% na pagtugon sa pangangailangan ng mga players ay siguro po'y hindi naibigay ang lahat 'yung isangdaang porsyento. Subalit nagpapasalamat pa rin ako dahil ano pa man ang kinaya ng budget ng programang ito, ay napakalaking tulong sa mga mag-aaral, players at coaches." - Coach and PESS Coordinator</i>
Healing and Firming Families for a More Holistic Education- HAFFMHE		
		<i>"Opo dahil sa mga pagkukulang ng mga magulang sa kanilang mga anak ay natutugunan ng mga teachers." - separated</i> <i>"Nakatulong po sa amin kahit limitado ang naibigay ay nakatulong sa amin." - widowed</i> <i>"Natutugunan ang problema na dapat solusyunan. Nakakain kami dahil nabigyan at nakalibre ng pagkain," - orphaned</i>
Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage		
		<i>"Natutugunan po dahil napaliwanagan po ang mga kabataan at nang matakot din po na mangatipan at magbuntis." - former student</i> <i>"Isa itong hakbang upang matugunan ang problema sa ating lipunan sapagkat dahil dito nagkaroon ng ka alaman ang mga kabataan patungkol sa lumalaganap na teen age pregnancy." - former student</i>

Government school systems, such as BNHS, have limited resources to achieve their objectives, making efficient resource use a primary goal of school activities. Through the ASPs of BNHS, issues arising from the school's budget scheme were addressed, and appropriate actions were taken. Astbury (2022) confirmed that these alternatives and strategies to rectify the issues are more suitable as short-term solutions, but they are still preferable to students' achieving goals that exceed the school's financial capabilities.

One hundred percent of the beneficiaries and respondents agreed that the ASPs had addressed the problems. The ASP Send Off Program for Players enabled the players to focus solely on their preparation for the competition, without being distracted by any other aspects. One beneficiary player commented and overwhelmingly expressed:

"Malaking bagay sa isang player 'yung may basic needs ka na baon papunta sa competition."

The MIMAROPARAA Player commented,

"Nakakabawas bigat sa isipin ng player 'yung mga pangangailangang ganun."

Added to this assistance to him as a player was pocket money for the regional event.

"Pag MIMAROPARAA nga po ay may cash allowance pa ako," he added to his statement.

For the former provincial medalist in Taekwondo, there was more than the goods during the send-off program,

"Nabibigyan ng karagdagang pangangailangan ang mga manlalaro...binigyan din po kami ng dagdag kaalaman at impormasyon bago pa mag-distribute ng mga goody bags."

According to Amaro (2020), three of the most significant participation takeaways that students carry with them into their post-graduation years are: (a) a greater sense of self-confidence in forming relationships with others and possessing an increased capacity for empathy; (b) improving self-awareness and consequently understanding the impact of their actions on others; and (c) laying the groundwork for enduring fitness routines.

Figure 5 illustrates the graph of in-kind and cash donations for provincial players of Buenavista District.

Figure 5

Cash and In-Kind Donations for Send-Off Program for Players School Year 2018-2019 and School Year 2019-2020

Legend:

School Year 2018-2019

School Year 2019-2020

*No Provincial Meet in SY 2020-2022 due to Covid19 pandemic

Source: BNHS Sports Coordinator, Guidance Offices of Buenavista NHS and the Division of Marinduque Sports Committee
 Figure 5, "Cash and In-Kind Donations for the Send-Off Program for Players, School Year 2018–2019 and School Year 2019–2020," illustrates the progress of in-kind and cash donations over the previous years of implementing the Send-Off Program for Players. The graph reflects the progressive support of donors and sponsors for the players, indicating a positive community response and successful implementation of the ASP.

In the school year 2018–2019, there were 199 beneficiaries of the program. The school, through the Guidance Offices, incurred seventeen thousand nine hundred pesos (P 17,900.00) in cash donations and received in-kind donations worth thirteen thousand nine hundred twenty-six pesos (P 13,926.00), totalling thirty-one thousand eight hundred twenty-six pesos (P 31,826.00). For the school year 2019–2020, there were 205 beneficiaries, with total cash donations of twenty-three thousand three hundred ninety

pesos (P 23,390.00) and in-kind donations worth eighteen thousand seven hundred eighty-six pesos (P 18,786.00).

The data reveal an increase in cash donations in the second year of implementation and a decrease in in-kind donations. This trend indicates that the organizers and proponents of the ASP successfully gained the trust of donors and sponsors. The increasing total amount of donations over the years justified the community's support for the BNHS project. The latest Send-Off Program saw an even greater total of ninety-four thousand five hundred sixty-five pesos and twenty-five centavos (P 94,565.25).

The School PESS Coordinator at BNHS noted that while the problem has not been fully addressed, the efforts put into the project are appreciated.

“Subalit nagpapasalamat pa rin ako dahil ano pa man ang kinaya ng budget ng programang ito, ay napakalaking tulong sa mga mag-aaral, players at coaches.”

Figure 6 shows the trend of the medals received by Buenavista District in the previous implementations of the ASP.

Figure 6

Medals Received by Buenavista District in the Provincial Meet from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2022-2023

Legend:

*No Provincial Meet in 2020-2022 due to Covid19 pandemic

Source: DepEd Division of Marinduque Sports Committee

For the ASP Send-Off Program for Players, there was noticeable progress in the number of medals received by the district, where most of the players came from BNHS, as reflected in Figure 6, "Medals Received by Buenavista District in the Provincial Meet From 2018 to 2023." This figure clearly shows a positive impact following the implementation of the ASP.

Each year, the line graph in Figure 6 indicates a progressive increase in the total number of medals won by the Buenavista District. This significant improvement in the performance of players and coaches in the Provincial Meet is evident from the data. In 2018, Buenavista District earned 19 bronzes, 11 silvers, and seven gold medals. In 2019, the district earned 20 bronzes, eight silver, and eight gold medals. By the latest 2023 games, the district had earned 25 bronzes, 20 silvers, and seven gold medals. The consistent improvement in performance each year suggests that the ASP has had a positive influence on the players' achievements during the competition.

The beneficiaries of the program widely believed in its benefits. One program beneficiary, a separated parent, viewed the ASP as a substitute for a father's unfulfilled commitment to his children, highlighting the program's positive personal impact.

"Opo dahil sa mga pagkukulang ng mga magulang sa kanilang mga anak ay natutugunan ng mga teachers."

The other beneficiary parent appreciated the assistance although it was limited. "Nakatulong po sa amin kahit limitado ang naibigay ay nakatulong sa amin."

A beneficiary student and child stated that they were able to eat because of the ASP, *"Natutugunan ang problema na dapat solusyunan. Nakakain kami dahil nabigyan at nakalibre ng pagkain,"*

Beneficiaries of the Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage Forum believe that the project addressed the problem and that they learned something from the ASP.

"Natutugunan po dahil napaliwanagan po ang mga kabataan at nang matakot din po na mangatipan at magbuntis." stated by one of the attendees of the forum.

Added to this is the perception of the beauty queen, another attendee.

"Isa itong hakbang upang matugunan ang problema sa ating lipunan sapagkat dahil dito nagkaroon ng ka alaman ang mga kabataan patungkol sa lumalaganap na teenage pregnancy."

Figure 4, "Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage Cases in Buenavista National High School from School Year 2018–2019 to School Year 2022–2023," shows a declining trend in these cases during the implementation of the ASP. This indicates the program's success in raising awareness among students about their reproductive health.

Khan et al. (2019) stated that given the mutual interaction of health and education, the school-based approach has been effective in behavior-oriented education in numerous cases. Adolescent girls who receive health education in school are more conscious of

their personal health and better equipped to safeguard their reproductive health from potential risks.

Adopting a school has advantages for all involved. Adopting the school gives the person or the organization a receives positive public relations because of its connection to such a significant segment of the community. The involvement helps the school because it exposes pupils to enriching programs that broaden their knowledge. The teaching personnel and the school head receives assistance in their endeavors. The parents feel less burdened in the financial aspect due to the extended assistance of the adopting entity that caters the needs of their children. Most of all the children will feel the support not only from their parents but also from the entire community. This will somehow encourage them to make a change for the betterment of their status in life.

Table 25 presents the statements of beneficiaries regarding the adopt-a-school programs held by Buenavista National High School. Their feedback reflects the effectiveness of these programs and their contributions to the students, parents, and community members. Additionally, the beneficiaries expressed their thoughts on the potential for other schools to emulate such programs.

Table 25

Emulation of Buenavista National High School’s Adopt-a-School Programs

Send-off Program for Players		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
BNHS' ASPs Emulation	ASPs of BNHS will be imitated or will try to be implemented by other schools or institutions to radiate their positive effects, further strengthen connections between the school and the community, and yield a better outcome for the various aspects of the learning environment.	<p><i>“Siguro po ay dapat itong gayahin, palaganapin sa anumang paaralan sa lalawigan sapagkat malaking tulong po ito lalong lalo na sa DepEd na kung saan ay kapos o kulang ang budget ng departamento sa sports development kaya’t kailangan po natin ng mga bukas palad na mga tao, naorganizer na tutulong sa mga ganitong programa para sa mga players.” - Coach</i></p> <p><i>“Maganda pong gawin ng bawat school ito. Halimbawa sa lahat ng schools ng Buenavista Cluster. Kapag ganyan po</i></p>
Send-off Program for Players		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
		<p><i>mas marami maiibigay sa players ng BNHS dahil yung programa po sa atin ay pang buong Buenavista ay kasama pati ang mga coaches sa pina babaunan ninyo. Mas mararamdaman po pati ng mga players ang suporta ng bawat community nila, mas inspired.” - Player</i></p> <p><i>“Mas okay na ibahagi ng bawat paaralan ang ganitong programa. Nakaka-inspire sa mga manlalaro na mapagbuti ang kanyang paglalaro sa napiling event. Sa ganitong paraan hindi malayo na maka-produce ang Buenavista ng isang National Player.” - Player</i></p>

Healing and Firming Families for a More Holistic Education- HAFFMHE		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
BNHS' ASPs Emulation		<p>"Ako po'y naniniwala na dapat subukan o isagawa ng ibang paaralan. Makakatulong po ito sa mga magulang at mga mag-aaral. Dahil sa kakulangan sa kinikita. Isa itong karagdang pangangailangan sa araw-araw. Lalo na at aisa akong nakita. Ako'y naga sari-sari store lang. Ang makatawid sa pangangailangan sa ilang araw ay malaking bagay na." - Separated</p> <p>"Opo. Marami ang makikinabang. Kung kaya ng school (BNHS) ay bakit hindi gawin dahil ang daming nangangailangan. Napakalaking tulong na po 'nun para sa isang pamilya at nagataasan ang mga presyo ng bilihin. Hindi po ako nahiya pumila at 'yun ay biyaya." - Widowed</p> <p>"Opo. Maraming matutuwa dahil makakatanggap sila ng biyaya galing sa school." - Orphan</p>
Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
BNHS' ASPs Emulation		<p>"Dapat na maging proyekto ng ibang schools ito para mas marami ang nakaka-alam ng magiging buhay nila at maging handa upang maiwasan ang mga posibleng dahilan upang maging batang ina o ama. Para mas malaman nila ang hirap ng buhay. Mas maunti ang mabubuntis ng maaga at matatakot dahil sa mga videos na napapanuod." - Former student</p> <p>"Nararapat lang na isagawa ito ng ibang mga paaralan, dahil ang pagco-conduct ng mga symposium at orientation ay isa sa mabisang paraan upang maiwasan ng mga kabataan ang maagang pagkakaroon ng anak at pamilya, kung saan dito papasok ang comprehensive sex education, self-awareness, STD/HIV prevention and youth development." - Former student</p>

One hundred percent (100%) of the respondents believe that ASPs at BNHS have beneficial impacts and that other schools or institutions may implement them.

The first Adopt-a-School program of BNHS to be tried out by the other schools is the Send-off Program for players. As stated in one of the player's responses, *"Nakaka-inspire sa mga manlalaro na mapagbuti ang kanyang paglalaro sa napiling event. Sa ganitong paraan hindi malayo na maka-produce ang Buenavista ng isang National Player."*

With this kind of project, players could feel the support they need evident in another player's response, *"Mas mararamdaman po pati ng mga players ang suporta ng bawat community nila, mas inspired."*

As a government institution, the school is tasked under Program Objective 1 of DepEd Order No. 25 s. 2015, or the Implementing Guidelines on the Special Program in Sports,

to not only develop the academic aspect of the child but also its sports skills. BNHS strongly supports this advocacy of the department and be one of those pushes that could encourage athletes to pursue their passion for sports.

According to one of the players, if Send Off Program will be implemented by other schools,

“...mas marami maiibigay sa players ng BNHS dahil yung programa po sa atin ay pang buong Buenavista...”

Based on one of the coaches, not only does the entire district benefit from the outputs of such kinds of projects related to sports but also DepEd in the larger sense.

“... malaking tulong po ito lalong lalo na sa DepEd na kung saan ay kapos o kulang ang budget ng departamento sa sports development ...”

Likewise, HAFFMHE must try to implement in other schools to strengthen the connection among family members and lighten their burden in relation to everyday needs occasionally.

Schools have historically prioritized family and community engagement in grades K–12. However, as pupils get older, parental involvement in schooling tends to decrease. According to some research, parental participation dropped by up to 17% between middle school and the third through fifth grades. This pattern, along with the continued difficulties in academic recovery, highlights the necessity of including and assisting more district community members in the K–12 school environment (Hanover Research, 2023).

“Makakatulong po ito sa mga magulang at mga mag-aaral. Dahil sa kakulangan sa kinikita... Lalo na at aisa akong nakita... Ang makatawid sa pangangailangan sa ilang araw ay malaking bagay na.”, a separated parent stated.

Even though the supplies received by the families were very limited, their value is immeasurable for the beneficiaries,

“Napakalaking tulong na po ‘nun para sa isang pamilya at naga-taasan ang mga presyo ng bilinghin.”, the reply of a single parent.

For families with a single working parent, having relief from a few days of expenses for their basic needs is significant. Beneficiaries may perceive the support of both the school and the community towards families like theirs when they receive these items. The school demonstrates concern not only for the education of its students but also for the welfare of the entire family. Delgado (2019) noted in his paper that experts on parental involvement in education assert that a family's level of engagement in a child's education is the most reliable predictor of that child's success. When students feel supported by their parents, they become more motivated and develop a passion for learning.

Furthermore, during the Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage, respondents expressed agreement that the ASP should be adopted by other schools because it would greatly assist in educating the younger generation about these prevalent issues. One

respondent, reflecting on personal experiences of failing to apply learned lessons, responded affirmatively when asked if other schools should implement similar projects.

“Para mas malaman nila ang hirap ng buhay. Mas maunti ang mabubuntis ng maaga at matatakot dahil sa mga videos na napapanuod.”

According to one of the respondents, it is better to educate teenagers because they will be warned not to do something abruptly and unprepared for an unexpected consequence.

The other respondent of the ASP believes that this must be done by other schools as an effective way of preventing teenagers from getting too early into forming families.

“...dito papasok ang comprehensive sex education, self-awareness, STD/HIV prevention, and youth development.”

With the ongoing implementation trend of the ASP Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage by the RHU in Buenavista, secondary schools in the district may not necessarily need to adopt the program outright. Instead, they could integrate follow-up sessions into other subject areas to serve as constant reminders of the information and lessons learned from the forum. The RHU of the LGU has been extending its services to secondary schools in the district by emulating the ASP Program of BNHS, facilitated by the annual coordination between BNHS and the RHU. This collaboration is expected to lead to a reduction in cases related to teenage pregnancy and early marriage, and with follow-up initiatives at home, it may foster the development of more responsible couples in the coming years.

The ASPs have proven to be beneficial for the beneficiaries, who suggest implementing similar programs in other schools to better understand the outcomes, based on their positive experiences.

However, beneficiaries are not the sole beneficiaries of the ASPs; BNHS itself has gained intangible benefits from implementing them. While these may not be immediately evident in material aspects or recognition, they likely manifest in strengthened connections between the school and its clientele, their families, and the community at large. Various individuals involved in each project may have experienced realizations, and there are likely underlying benefits that only future generations can fully appreciate, especially through the community's response to BNHS's needs and those of its future clientele.

Based on the School Report Card (SRC)

San Miguel (2019) elucidated that the guidelines for conducting the planning process at the school level were established through the release of DepED Order 44 series of 2015, titled "Guidelines on Enhanced School Improvement Planning (SIP) and School Report Card (SRC)." The Department of Education reiterated that the SRC is a key component of the DepEd School-Based Management initiative, to be prepared twice a year by each school during the school year. Its purpose is to enhance shared governance, raise community and stakeholder awareness, and encourage greater community involvement in improving the learning environment at the school.

Parafina (2018) further elaborated that the SRC provides comprehensive information on all essential aspects of the school. In this paper, the summarized SRC data of BNHS somehow reflects the differences or contributions made by the ASPs of BNHS, which have contributed to the school's current level of performance as indicated in the SRC.

Table 26 presents the data included in the school report card of Buenavista National High School, essential for measuring and addressing the inquiries covered by this study. This data serves to justify the improvement in the school's performance in previous school years.

Table 26

Summarized Data on the School Report Card of Buenavista National High School from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2021-2022

School Year	Enrollment	Health & Nutritional Status		Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment		Funding Sources	School Award & Recognition	Status of Annual Implementation Plan	Stakeholders Participation
		Inside Normal	Outside Normal	With Masters Degree	Without Masters Degree				
2021-2022	1510	N/A	N/A	38	17	MOOE 1, 577,999.61, Donations 76, 560.00 HAFFMHE	2National 4Regional 4Division 1District	100% Completed	Contributions & Participations by Private & Public Sectors
2020-2021	1,500	N/A	N/A	45	9	MOOE- 1,578,000.00 Donations - 61, 101.00	Not Available	100% Completed	Not Available

School Year	Enrollment	Health & Nutritional Status		Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment		Funding Sources	School Award & Recognition	Status of Annual Implementation Plan	Stakeholders Participation
		Inside Normal	Outside Normal	With Masters Degree	Without Masters Degree				
2019-2020	1354	768	103	33	21	MOOE- 1,578, 000, Canteen- 16, 938.00, Donations- 47, 150.00, Others - 160, 000.00	1National 1Division 4District	100% Completed	Financial Support 47,150 Private Individual & LGU Municipality
2018-2019	1355					Alumni Donation 100, 000.00 School Grounds			

School Year	Availability of Books	Rate of Dropouts by Cause	Promotion Rate	Literacy Level		Learner-Teacher Ratio	Learner-Classroom Ratio	Learner-Toilet Ratio	Learner-Seat Ratio
				English	Filipino				
2021-2022	75.03	0.6 % Domestic Related Factors	100.00	N/A	N/A	40.38	6:27 Lacking 7 Classrooms	54:1 Lacking 2 toilets	100:71 Lacking if 429 seats
2020-2021	75.79	3.47% Cause-Individual-Related Factors	99.81	N/A	N/A	40.38	6:27	54:1 Lacking 2 toilets	100:71 Lacking 429 seats
2019-2020	83.78	3.84 Cause-Individual-Related Factors	95.37	40.38	57.93	40.38	6:27 Lacking 2 Classrooms	48:1	100:79 Lacking 283 seats
2018-2019	N/A	2.8 Cause-Individual-Related Factors	95.81	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: Principal's Office of Buenavista National High School

In Table 26, "Summarized Data on the School Report Card of Buenavista National High School from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2021-2022," information has been compiled from the past four consecutive school years. However, certain aspects of BNHS's SRC mentioned in this paper, such as the teacher-to-student ratio, chair-to-student ratio, and books-to-student ratio, were not observed during the COVID-19 pandemic. Data for the SY 2018-2019 were particularly limited. The data summarized and presented here were gathered and provided to the researcher during the period when this study was conducted.

Each category of the SRC will be comprehensively discussed in the following sections, accompanied by graphical presentations to facilitate a better understanding of the data collected during face-to-face interviews with the respondents.

Enrolment Per School Year

Figure 6 is the graph of Buenavista National High School's enrolment from school year 2018-2019 to school year 2021-2022 extracted from the SRC of the school.

Below is the graph of Buenavista National High School's enrolment from school year 2018-2019 to school year 2021-2022 extracted from the SRC of the school.

Figure 6

*Buenavista National High School
Enrolment Per School Year from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2021-2022*

Source: Buenavista National High School School Report Card

In the school year 2018–2019, enrolment stood at 1,355 students. Subsequently, there was a slight increase 1,354 students in the school year 2019–2020, followed by a more significant rise 1,500 students in 2020–2021, and 1,510 students in 2021–2022. These figures indicate a progressive increase, suggesting that members of the community had confidence in BNHS's ability to accommodate their children and provide the necessary education for them to become competent individuals, despite other schools in the neighboring barangays.

Health and Nutritional Status

In the SY 2018-2019, no data were entered. However, in SY 2019-2020, there were 768 students within the normal range and 103 students outside the normal range, representing almost 25% of the total student population. Due to the pandemic, no weighing of students was conducted, making it difficult to gauge the effectiveness of the ASP's contribution to the school's progress. However, the ASP HAFMHE was implemented in SY 2021-2022 to support the nutritional needs of learners, although this was not reflected in the SRC under donations, possibly due to the failure to update the school's SRC. The school anticipated a progressive improvement in the learners' nutritional status during the pandemic, with support from the Department of Education in the form of health supplies allocated from the MOOE, including face masks, alcohol, gloves, and sanitizers issued to both teachers and learners. Additionally, the LGU provided health supplies for learners, which were reflected in the SRC counterpart of the LGU.

Availability of Books

Below is the graph of Buenavista National High School's availability of books from school year 2019-2019 to school year 2021-2022 extracted from the SRC of the school.

Figure 8

*Buenavista National High School School Report Card
Availability of Books from School Year 2019-2020 to School Year 2021-2022*

Source: Buenavista National High School School Report Card

There was a decline in the percentage availability of books. Data in the graph show that there was 83.78% in the SY 2019-2020, 75.79% in the SY 2020-2021, and 75.03% in the SY 2021-2022. Deliveries of modules and books were made in the SY 2022-2023. No ASP for books during these school years.

In addition to having no access to books during the pandemic, few students nowadays read books; instead, they read online using the application or through social media for their activities.

Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment

Next noteworthy element of the SRC is the number of teachers in each category of the Highest Educational Attainment. It shows that the number of faculty members who were taking masteral degrees progressively increased from 33 in SY 2019-2020 to 45 in the following year, SY 2020-2021. The number of teachers taking masteral degree decreased in SY 2021-2022, having 38 only. In this period, localization was availed of by some of the faculty members who were presently residing in distant municipalities.

The positive movement in the number of teachers with masteral degrees was due to the encouragement of the school head during LAC sessions for the faculty members to further their education because of the new guidelines for the promotion of teachers. Added to this is the awareness of the teachers that they need to further their knowledge in serving the technology-updated generation of learners.

Funding Sources

Figure 8 reflects Buenavista National High School's funding sources from school year 2018-2019 to school year 2021-2022 extracted from the SRC of the school.

Below is the graph of Buenavista National High School's funding sources from school year 2018-2019 to school year 2021-2022 extracted from the SRC of the school.

Figure 8

Buenavista National High School

Funding Sources from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2021-2022

Source: Buenavista National High School School Report Card

The indicator "Sources of Funds" consistently included two main counterparts: Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and donations, for the four previous school years at BNHS. The total funding sources ranged between 1,578,000.00 PHP to 1,803,000.00 PHP. Figure 8, "Buenavista National High School Funding Sources SY 2018-2019 to SY 2021-2022," directly reflects the percentage share of the ASPs of the school and the counterpart of the other resources. Donations through the ASPs were an indispensable portion of the funding sources for Buenavista National High School and any public schools.

In SY 2018-2019, donations from alumni, estimated at 100,000.00 PHP for concreting the school grounds, were not reflected in the SRC of the school.

In SY 2019-2020, the total fund was 1,802,088.00 PHP. In this included 1,578,000.00 PHP MOOE; 16,938.00 PHP from canteen shares; 47,150.00 PHP in donations; and other unspecified resources comprising 160,000.00 PHP.

For SY 2020-2021, the total funding source was 1,639,101.00 PHP. The MOOE allotment was 1,578,000.00 PHP, with total donations amounting to 61,101.00 PHP.

In the previous school year 2021-2022, the total funding source was 1,654,559.61 PHP. This comprised MOOE with 1,577,999.61 PHP, and donations worth 76,560.00 PHP.

These data reflect the increasing needs of BNHS over the previous four school years. As the demand of the learners increases, the ASP share also increases. This indicates that stakeholders and other community members can sustain the assistance needed by the school each year.

School Award & Recognition

Below is the graph of Buenavista National High School's school award and recognition from the school year 2018-2019 to school year 2021-2022 extracted from the SRC of the school.

Figure 9

*Buenavista National High School School Report Card
School Award and Recognition from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2021-2022*

Legend:

 - National Level
 - Regional Level
 - Division Level

Note: Only the number of awards per level was indicated not the rank obtained from the level.

Source: Buenavista National High School School Report Card

The School Awards and Recognitions received by BNHS are the most notable part of the SRC. Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, the school continued to excel. In SY 2019–2020, BNHS received six awards: four at the District Level, one at the Division Level, and one at the National Level. However, in 2021-2022, BNHS achieved a remarkable 11 awards: two at the National Level, four at the Regional Level, four at the Division Level, and one at the District Level. This significant increase in awards nearly doubled the school's previous achievements.

The courage of the participants to compete during the pandemic can be attributed to the encouragement and support of the coaches, teachers, parents, and the school head, alongside the abundant talent among the students. Financial support provided through the ASP of the school also played a crucial role in enabling participation in these competitions.

Status of Annual Implementation Plan

The Status of Annual Implementation Plan maintained a one hundred percent (100%) yield by the school over the previous three school years, from 2019–2020 to 2021–2022. This clearly indicates that the school faithfully executed the set annual programs and projects in the School Improvement Plan through collaborative efforts from various components of the learning environment, both internal and external.

Stakeholders' Participation, as emphasized by Siles (n.d.), involves shared understanding and active involvement in decision-making processes, leading to empowerment and shared project ownership. This indicator strongly supports the successful implementation of the school's ASPs, consistently demonstrating their integral role in every aspect of the school's endeavors.

Before the pandemic hit in SY 2019–2020, the school received financial support totaling 47,150 PHP from private individuals and the LGU. However, there was a decline in stakeholders' participation in SY 2020–2021 due to the peak of COVID-19. Fortunately, after the pandemic subsided in SY 2021-2022, the school received a total 863,543 PHP from contributions and participation of the private and public sectors, once again facilitated through the ASPs of the school.

Stakeholders' Participation

Siles (n.d.) emphasized that stakeholder participation in the project entails having a shared understanding and taking part in the decision-making process. Empowerment and shared project ownership result from it, which means the project should begin with consultation and end with decisions made in unison in order to maximize involvement.

This indicator strongly justified the successful implementation of the school's ASPs by remarkably setting its consistent piece of the pie in every endeavor of the school. Before the pandemic enraged the school year 2019–2020, the school was able to avail financial support with a total worth of forty-seven thousand one hundred fifty pesos (47,150 PHP) from private individuals and from the LGU of the municipality. There was a gap in the

stakeholders' participation in the school year 2020–2021 due to the peak level of COVID-19. Right after the pandemic ends in the school year 2021-2022, the school was able to receive a total of eight hundred sixty-three thousand five hundred forty-three pesos (863,543 PHP) from the contributions and participation of the private and public sectors. Again, these were under the ASPs of the school.

Rate of Dropouts by Cause

Below is the graph of Buenavista National High School's dropout rate from school year 2018-2019 to school year 2021-2022 extracted from the SRC of the school.

Figure 11

*Buenavista National High School
Dropout Rate from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2021-2022*

Source: Buenavista National High School School Report Card

An indication of the efficacy of a nation's educational system is the percentage of students that drop out and miss school. They are important indicators of the challenges the nation's education system may face in the future (Samuel, 2023).

Another positive indicator of a performing school is the declining number of drop-outs. For BNHS, it decreased with a big difference from 52 students to 9 students. The increasing data on enrollment revealed that the school can encourage students to finish their studies despite the challenges they are facing. Nonetheless, data on the drop-out

rate showed a significant decrease from 52 in the first two years to 9 in the current school year, 2022-2023. This could be attributed to the situation during the pandemic and the campaign by BNHS to go back to school. The common reasons for students to drop out of school in the school years 2018–2019 and 2019–2020 were individual-related factors, while in the school year 2020–2021, it was domestic-related factors. These were the target objectives of the guidance offices in formulating the ASPs for the school.

Promotion Rate

BNHS maintained a high promotion rate ranging from 95% to 100% over the past four school years. This consistency indicates the school's commitment to advancing students to subsequent grades or graduation levels. The small fluctuations observed in the promotion rates are minimal and likely within the expected variation.

Literacy Level

Limited data were available for the literacy level aspect of the SRC, with data only available for SY 2019-2020 showing percentages in English and Filipino. This scarcity of data may hinder a comprehensive analysis of literacy trends over time.

Learner-Teacher Ratio

BNHS faces challenges in maintaining an ideal learner-teacher ratio due to a lack of classrooms. Despite efforts such as assigning co-advisers and maximizing available space, the average number of students per advisory remains high, ranging from 45-55 students. This situation underscores the urgent need for additional classrooms to improve the learning environment.

Learner-Classroom Ratio

The school struggles with inadequate classroom space, particularly for junior high school teachers who lack faculty rooms. The shortage of classrooms has persisted over the past two school years, with the current need estimated at ten (10) classrooms to meet DepEd's standards. The delay in classroom construction due to space constraints highlights the importance of collaboration with stakeholders to address infrastructure needs.

Learner-Toilet Ratio

Despite having functional and clean toilets, BNHS faces challenges in maintaining an adequate learner-to-toilet ratio, as the increasing student population has outpaced toilet facilities' capacity. The limited space available presents obstacles to expanding toilet facilities, indicating the need for creative solutions to address this issue.

Learner-Seat Ratio

BNHS experiences a shortage of seats, with the number of lacking chairs increasing over the past two school years. The school is exploring strategies to remodel existing chairs

to meet students' needs. However, the persistent shortage underscores the necessity for additional resources to ensure adequate seating for all learners.

Overall, while BNHS has made significant strides in various aspects of its SRC over the past four years, challenges such as infrastructure limitations persist. Collaboration with stakeholders and creative solutions will be essential in addressing these challenges to further improve the school's performance and meet the evolving needs of its learners.

Keys to the Successful Implementation of Buenavista National High School's Adopt-a-School Programs

For projects to be implemented successfully and yield the best results, a strong foundation is necessary. The implementing group can guarantee project success by efficiently managing a project strategy during the planning phase. Eby (2022) seconded that thorough planning can determine the success of any endeavor. While Florida Tech (2018) adheres to the statement that success is possible by maintaining its alignment and progress facilitated by providing everyone with clarity, openness, and consistency in the workflow process.

For BNHS, a strong connection with the community and stakeholders is the best to guarantee the success of every program or project launched by a school.

Table 27

Keys to Successful Implementation of the Project Send-off Program for Players

Send-off Program for Players		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Connection and Cooperation	The strong link between the school and the various aspects of the community that makes every ASP of BNHS successful	<i>"Palagay ko po 'yung pagtutulongan ng lahat ng myembro ng community. Hindi lang teachers, students, magulang at iba pang tao. Nag-i-extend sila ng suporta sa players sa abot ng kanilang makakaya."</i> - MIMAROPARAA Player
Proponent or Organizer's Effort	Efforts of the proponent or organizers played a major part for the success of the ASP	<i>"Naging successful ang programa at epektibo. 'Yung concern at pagtutulongan siguro ang nagbigay buhay upang maging successful ang bawat send-off program for players."</i> - Taekwondo Player <i>"Unang-una kaya naging matagumpay ang programa ay dahil sa organizer. Kung walang organizer ay hindi ito magpu-pursue kahit pa may mga donors. Hindi ito mama-materialize. So, para sa akin dahil sa mga organizers ay naisasakatuparan ang mga gawain katulong ang mga donors."</i> <i>"Ako'y naniniwala na matagumpay ang programa dahil nagamit nila ang mga pangangailangan habang sila'y andun sa tatlo hanggang limang araw na palaro."</i> - Coach

Healing and Firming Families for a More Holistic Education- HAFFMHE		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Teachers' Effort	Components of the school took effort in extending services to the learners and their families.	<i>"Naging matagumpay ang proyekto dahil nagsisikap ang mga guro na mabigyan solusyon ang mga problema ng mga mag-aaral maging akademik man o pangtahanan. Sa abot ng kanilang makakaya ay piliit nilang abutin ang bawat pangangailangan ng bawat mag-aaral."</i> - Separated
Accountability	There is an assurance that BNHS is responsible and could deliver the service set for the specific ASP.	<i>"Matagumpay ang proyekto dahil nabigyan ang lahat ng dapat makinabang at dahil 'yan sa pagsisikap ng mga guro."</i> - Widowed <i>"Maraming nangangailangan ang natulungan kaya naging matagumpay ang project na mga walang maayos na trabaho atkapos sa buhay."</i> - Orphan
Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage		
Theme	Definition	Common Responses
Successful ASP Effort of the school, Guidance and LGU	The assessment of the implemented project. The determining factors towards project's successful implementation	<i>"Successful ang programa dahil napanuod na nila at napakinggan nila ang mga maaaring mangyari sa buhay nila."</i> - Teenage Pregnancy Program Beneficiary <i>"Ang pagtutulungan ng LGU, paaralan at Guidance Office and naging susi upang maging matagumpay ang proyekto. Ang pagkakaroon ng madalasang symposium ukol sa isyu ay isang magandang paraan at ganun din ang pagkakatat ng kaalaman sa pinakamabilis na pamamaraan."</i> - Teenage Pregnancy Program Beneficiary

The Center for Educational Innovation (n.d.) enumerated the characteristics of successful team projects. Among the characteristics of successful team projects are well-defined collaboration, relevance and authenticity, and team accountability. At least two of these are being practiced by BNHS based on the statements of the respondents: collaboration and authenticity and team accountability.

The first key is the collaboration of the various components of the community. Senjaya (2019) affirmed that all stakeholders must engage fully and intelligently for a school administrator to be successful. In this include the MLGU,

LGU, teachers, parents, members of the different civic organizations, and others.

Collaboration, which is always practiced at BNHS and in any public school. In every endeavor of the school, coordination with the various organizations in the school is consistent. The programs of the school are extended to the community for collaboration and assistance. Organizations, whether school-related, government-related, or non-civic, are being involved out of willingness to ensure their participation in accomplishing the endeavor. The responses of the interviewees could justify the intensity of their participation in every project of the school.

"Palagay ko po 'yung pagtutulungan ng lahat ng myembro ng community. Hindi lang teachers, students, magulang at iba pang tao. Nag-i-extend sila ng suporta sa player sa abot ng kanilang makakaya."

Same with the comment of another beneficiary from teenage pregnancy and early marriage, *“Ang pagtutulungan ng LGU, paaralan at Guidance Office and naging susi upang maging matagumpay ang proyekto.”*

A further justification is provided by a remark from another player benefit stating that success was accomplished through the cooperation of the many components.

“...Yung concern at pagtutulungan siguro ang nagbigay buhay upang maging successful ang bawat send-off program for players.”

The second key determinant based on the statements of the respondents, accountability. Under the leadership of the school principal, accountability is always included as one of the main considerations of the implementing body. As a response from the principal for Table 6, Pre-implementation Phase of Adopt-a-School Program in Terms of Reasons for Selecting the School as Recipient of the Program, this is one of the possible reasons for choosing BNHS as a beneficiary of a project.

“Another ay accountability, yung properly accounted ang donations nila. May report tayo.”

The last key to the successful implementation of the school's ASPs were due to the efforts of the proponents. The efforts exerted by the project proponent or organizers of the ASPs that paved for the success of the programs.

One remarkable response from a beneficiary coach reiterated that the ASPs of the school became successful because of the organizers' efforts.

“Unang-una kaya naging matagumpay ang programa ay dahil sa organizer. Kung walang organizer ay hindi ito magpu-pursue kahit pa may mga donors. Hindi ito mama-materialize. So, para sa akin dahil sa mga organizers ay naisasakatuparan ang mga gawain katulong ang mga donors.”

Two of the parent beneficiaries of HAFFMHE stated that the success of the ASPs was solely attributable to the organizer's' efforts to address student issues through these projects.

“Sa abot ng kanilang makakaya ay pilit nilang abutin ang bawat pangangailangan ng bawat mag-aaral.”

Teachers, organizers, and other members of BNHS cannot achieve success in every attempt, despite their efforts. A successful ASP requires the participation of each component: PTA, SSG, stakeholders, organizations, and the entire community. Indeed, it takes a village to educate a child.

According to Khan (2020), the phrase "project success" refers to the particular standard decided upon by the client and the project team prior to the start of the project. After the project is completed, teams use these requirements, benchmarks, and deliverables to gauge project success.

ASPs at the school can be considered successful, with more of the characteristics being practiced by BNHS. The responses of the respondents and figures in the data gathered could justify the success of its implementation and coverage.

Adopt-a-School Programs of Buenavista National High School that could be benchmarked by other schools

A versatile method for examining and enhancing practically any part of a project or program in the school is benchmarking. This will support any essential modifications made by the head of the school and the implementing bodies beneficial for enhancing any procedures or programs (Intuit Mailchimp, n.d.).

With regular benchmarking the school will enable to develop precise, quantifiable short-term strategies grounded in current performance rather than past results, allowing for gradual performance gains over time. Transforming a performance deficit into performance leadership is the goal of surpassing the top performers (Gradecam, 2020).

Buenavista National High School is one of those schools that aims to better their services their clientele and at the same time widen and strengthen their connections with their stakeholders and members of the community in which the institution is rendering its services. For educational institutions to succeed and expand, benchmarking is essential. It gives schools the authority to set realistic goals, evaluate student performance honestly, and pursue greatness constantly.

In the dynamic realm of education, educational institutions are perpetually endeavoring to enhance their efficacy and furnish their students with optimal learning opportunities. In this circumstance, benchmarking is a useful tool that can help in this pursuit of excellence. By comparing performance and procedures with those of other organizations, benchmarking will enable BNHS to promote a continuous improvement culture.

ASPs of Buenavista National High School that may be benchmarked by other schools could be justified by the statements of the respondents after experiencing being part of the program as a beneficiary or as an implementer of the ASP. The respondents' statements play a great role in identifying those ASPs that truly contributed to the betterment of the school's services to the members of the community and that need to improve more to further its implementation.

The following are the ASPs that could be benchmarked by other schools:

A. Send Off Program for Players

The Send-off Program for Provincial Players started on 2018 upon the pursuance of the former principal, who happened to be always ushering the delegation of Marinduque to the MIMAROPARAA.

In this annual program, the players will be trained and oriented before leaving for the provincial competition. A day before their departure, each player and coaches of all the events in the entire cluster will be attending the send-off program in BNHS. They are

given goody bags with basic supplies they may need during the competition. Delegates of Buenavista Cluster to the regional competitions are also given pocket money. The supplies intended to lessen the expenses of the players and coaches and to inspire them.

With regards to the stages of its implementation, there were assigned teachers for the program. A synchronize acceptance of donations was through the guidance offices of the school. Donations were in two forms: in-kind and cash. For in-kind donations, every item being forwarded to the office is being recorded for the monitoring of the items' sufficiency. On the other hand, cash donations were recorded together with the screenshots of the donations through electronic cash forwarder of the designated person for the acceptance. For cash donations handed over to the school, these are being kept for a while waiting for the inventory of the items before the actual packing of the goods. Cash were used in purchasing the items that will complete the needed supplies of the players.

During the distribution phase of the goods, there were attendance sheets of the recipients on the day of the distribution per event. The coaches were there facilitating their players for the various parts of the send-off program. After some talks like orientations and the like topics needed by the player were discussed by the speakers, students will fall in line by event for the distribution.

After the implementation of the project is the accomplishment of the financial report to be confirmed by various committees ensuring transparency in the implementation of the entire program. These documents that compromised the financial report will be posted for the information and recognition of the donors.

With Send-off Program for Players, the spirit of encouragement and inspiration of the players are being ignited. They tend to play hard thinking that they are playing by representing the entire district and that there are people relying on them to be the best player they can be.

B. Healing and Firming for a More Holistic Education (HAFFMHE)

As a support to Forum on Teenage Pregnancy and Early Marriage, the school launched another short-term ASP in October 2021, the HAFFMHE. This supports orphaned, with solo parent, and with separated parents' students. The school believes that the student and parent beneficiaries somehow must be given importance and encouragement to continue supporting the education of their children.

This ASP was intended be conducted during Christmas break for the families to feel that BNHS was their extended family and was with them in celebrating the holidays.

In the implementation of the program, parents attended a short parenting seminar through the efforts of the invited speakers such as a resource person from DSWD, Sangguniang Bayan Member in-charge of the education sector and the School Guidance Designates. This aimed to remind the parents that regardless of the situation they are in as a parent, the welfare and education of the children is the main priority and that the school is with them in carrying their responsibilities.

Right after the program was the distribution of pack of goods with basic needs and something they could supposedly cook for the previous celebrations. Among these goods were: spaghetti pack, kilos of rice, sugar, milk, sardines, biscuits, shampoos and bath soaps.

This BE strengthens the link of the school to the community specifically with the learners and the parents. The school is taking its extra effort of extending its services to the community by becoming part of each household that needs patronage. Lastly, for the children and parent to realize and appreciate the presence of each other, that they need to stick together and work for the betterment of their future.

C. TEENAGE PREGNACY and EARLY MARRIAGE FORUM

This ASP of BNHS was initiated due to alarming number of cases of teenage pregnancy that involve the BNHS students, the best counteraction of the school is to create a program that will broaden the knowledge of the learners about reproductive health directly from a designated LGU health physician. This program is with the coordination to the Rural Health Unit (RHU) of Buenavista through the leadership of Dra. Eleanor Grate. Its implementation varies progressively each year.

During the first years of its implementation, students were lectured inside the classroom per section. The municipal physician wanted to maximize participation of the participants during the lecture and in the often forum. First, figures of cases in the entire province down to the local vicinity will be viewed and discuss. Next, the present situation of the family and the consequences the subjects are facing due to the situation they are engaged in. Students were also lectured on the disadvantages on health of teenage pregnancy and early marriage as well as the financial crisis they are suffering from. Pictures and Videos with statements of the subjects were presented to the attendees for greater realization of the possible situation they may be facing if ever engage in that situation. These aims to sway the minds of the students to go away from activities that are leading to early teenage pregnancy and early marriage.

At present, the RHU is in connection with the Population Commission in the implementation of the said project. This is an advantage for BNHS because the local government is one of the beneficiaries of the agency and is supporting projects in relation to population education that involve teenagers.

There was a decline in the number of cases specially in the senior high school students when the ASP started its annual implementation. This may be because students in the senior high school have better understanding with regards to sex education and are somehow informed and aware of the consequences they might be facing if ever engaged in such situations because of the forum. Further, cases in grade 8 consistently reappearing maybe because they were not included in those who attended the forum with the senior high school students.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Buenavista National High School's implementation of its ASPs greatly applies the School-Based Management, involving its stakeholders as its strong allies being strengthened by its recognition with consistent adherence to R.A. 8525 in accomplishing documents with an exemption in securing a MOA.
2. BNHS strictly initiated and formulated ASPs that cover only by R.A. 8525 provisions.
3. ASPs of BNHS have great effects to its beneficiaries that they felt moved for the efforts of the school and wish to pay back someday and even commending the ASPs to other schools for emulation.
4. There were significant changes in the data of the School Report Card in the previous school years that could be attributed as results of the ASPs parallel to the progressive changes of responses in supporting the ASPs.
5. ASPs of BNHS is always a success due to the cultured link of the school to the community members resulted from being liable of the different components of the school especially proponents of ASPs in every innovation launched.
6. The ASPs of the BNHS could be benchmarked by other schools to further improve the implementations and likewise be adapted and modified by other schools depending on the needs of the learners and the school.

Recommendations

Considering the presented research results and findings, the researcher wishes to recommend the following:

1. BNHS must keep and develop a record, or a database of the ASPs implemented by the school for future utilization, reference and MOA implementation. Likewise, the school may assign an office for Alumni and stakeholders inside the school campus and continue doing the Gabi ng Parangal for stakeholders with assigned presentations for them.
2. The school must maintain adherence to R.A. 8525 in relation to provisions of assistance to learners.
3. The school must find ways on how to continue short term ASPs with long term effects to continue the cultured link with the community.
4. Areas of improvement in the SRC where ASPs are useful could be identified and further given priorities for better and consistent results.

5. Efforts of the proponent or organizer in materializing the ASPs must be recognized, given credit to advance their career, and incentives to further encourage and inspire others in accomplishing extra efforts for the welfare of the learners.

6. Encourage other schools, after benchmarking the ASPs of BNHS, to develop their own ASPs that could bridge the needs and further improve the performance of the learners and the entire school.

Ethical Consideration

This study has set several considerations to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents and participants. Among the significant issues that were taken into consideration are informed consent, confidentiality, the anonymity of the respondents, and data protection.

During the face-to-face interview, the interviewees were informed about the purpose of conducting the interview and their part as respondents. Further, they were informed that an audio recording will be needed so as not to miss their statements, and notetaking will be necessary for the observation and additional details during the interview. A waiver was given to the respondents regarding the confidentiality of the information they did not want to disclose and their identity. An assurance that the information gathered will be used solely for its intended purposes and will be treated with confidentiality was sought, along with their cooperation. The cooperation of the respondents was valued and praised with the hope that this study will further promote the connections between the concerned individuals.

Acknowledgments

The researchers of this study would like to thank everyone who has offered guidance and encouragement throughout the years in pursuing this thesis.

First and foremost, to the researchers' thesis panelists; Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos Jr., and Dr. Joy S. Montejo, thank you for providing valuable feedback and suggestions. You truly molded the researchers to become more tenacious in the search for extensive wisdom;

To the researcher's very fastidious copy editor; Ms. Jessica L. Semilla, and language editor Ms. Anna Roffel M. Lozada, warmest appreciation for the insightful acumen while reviewing this paper;

To the respondents, for providing honest and valuable information, it truly amazed the researchers as they discovered the impacts and connections made by the ASPs to their lives;

To a friend Elsa F. Solito, who had served as the ultimate push and kept reminding inside to accomplish what had started and coincided;

Lastly, to the researchers' family members, Randy C. Sotto, for the immeasurable support and unwavering encouragement. And to the children, Rency, Janjan, and Sophia, for the sacrifices during the authors' absence from attending to their studies while struggling on their own.

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